
An Analysis of Dereverberation Algorithms on Music Signals

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ABSTRACT

The acquisition of a clean audio from distant microphones is often affected by the phenomenon of reverberation. On speech signals, the reverberation affects the intelligibility. Different ways to minimize this effect on speech signals have been studied during recent years because this is important in fields such as Automatic Speech Recognition. In music, the reverberation is an important aspect to take into account considering that it adds a sense of space and therefore, the effect is not negative. However, taking control over the reverberation could be interesting in order to clean the signal or maybe to manipulate it by changing the reverberation.

In this study one commercial plug-in, named as NML RevCon, has been studied and evaluated by using a set of instrumental sounds. The algorithm behind the plugin is one of the algorithms with most chance of success to achieve clean audio, and it is based on the multi step linear prediction technique.

The database was built from a set of anechoic sounds, convolved with three different impulses responses and dereverberated with the mentioned plug-in. Having the sounds in these three states was important in order to evaluate, later, the behaviour of the plug-in. Since the plugin has a set of control parameters, the dereverberated process has been done four times for each sample with different parameter settings.

The evaluation has been done by extracting the frequency-weighted segmental signal to noise ratio, from the comparison between the anechoic sample and the dereverberated sample. The results show that the speech sound achieves better results after the plug-in process than the instrument sounds. Taking into account only the instrument samples, the best results are achieved by the viola sounds.

In addition an analysis has been done of how the plugin behaves with different playing techniques. The results show that the sounds with well defined onsets, like pizzicato or staccato, have better results than the sounds like legato or detache.

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1 INTRODUCTION

This chapter introduces the topic that will be developed in this thesis and the motivations that justify this study.

1.1 Motivation

One of the acoustical phenomenon when a source is excited within a closed room is called reverberation. The fact that sound produced in the room will not disappear immediately after the sound source is shut off means that the sound will remain audible for a certain period of time [11].

The reverberation has pros and cons. In music processing, the sense of space that can be created with stereo or surround sound adds realism and often makes recorded music more attractive and enjoyable. Regarding the speech sounds, the reverberation has negative effects over the signal, affecting the intelligibility [16]. Therefore, it would be interesting to take control on the reverberation effects in order to minimize it.

Minimize the effect of the multipath components added to the signal by the room and its walls is the goal for the dereverberation process.

The dereverberation problem for speech signals has been studied due to its importance for certain applications, such as Automatic Speech Recognition (ASR) or speech enhancement [16]. Also, the interest in this field has been growing motivated by the increased use of hands-free devices. However, the dereverberation problem regarding instrumental sounds has not been studied at the same level as the speech signal, probably because its complexity and also because the reverberation helps to feel the sense of space, which is essential. Even this, the dereverberation over instrumental sounds is an interesting field. The dereverberation process over instrumental sounds might allow to clean the signal, keeping only the instrumental essence.

1.2 Goals

The main goal of the thesis is to study the behaviour of the existing dereverberation techniques for instrumental sounds. In order to achieve this goal, the first step will be to obtain the corresponding algorithm for each technique. Secondly it will be necessary to build a dataset to allow the experiments to run and finally the results will be reviewed.

1.3 Thesis overview

This dissertation is organized as follows. Section 2 describes the reverberation topic. First, the acoustic room principles are described. Second, the wave equation and the models of room acoustics are outlined. And finally, the effects that reverberation produces on the speech are explained. Section 3 describes the dereverberation topic. First, the dereverberation problem is presented. Second, different dereverberation techniques are outlined and then, existing algorithms and commercial products are mentioned. Section 4 explains the insights of the study carried out in this thesis; methodology, data collection, algorithm used, evaluation methods and data set selected. Section 5 and 6 analyze the results obtained from the study. Section 7 describes the conclusions. Section 8 points out the next steps to be carried out for further research. Finally, an appendix with the numerical results is attached in Section 9.

2 REVERBERATION

Reverberation is the effect produced by the combination of acoustic reflections when sound waves propagate in enclosed spaces [11]. If a source is considered to be emitting sound within a room, this sound will be reflected multiple times in a manner that depends on the geometry of the room as well as the nature of the reflective surfaces. In this chapter, the basis of the reverberation will be exposed.

2.1 Room acoustics

The effect of reverberation depends on the geometry of the source and the room as well as the nature of the reflective surfaces [11]. The way to measure the effect of any enclosure over the signal is by using the Acoustic Impulse Response (AIR). Whereas AIR is used to refer to the acoustic impulse response in general, it can also be limited to the acoustic context of the room. In this case, the impulse response is referred to as Room Impulse Response (RIR).

The RIR is defined as a pressure pattern at a particular point inside the room in response of an excitation pattern generated at another particular point. Between these two points the room's acoustical properties can be seen as a linear and time-invariant (LTI) filter [16]. The RIR of a linear system is the waveform that comes up at the output of the system when a Dirac δ -function is used as an input. The output $y(t)$ for an arbitrary input $x(t)$ is obtained by convolving the input $x(t)$ with the RIR $h(t)$,

$$y(t) = x(t) * h(t).$$

$$x(n) = s(n) * h(z) + b(n).$$

Where t means time, and $*$ is the mathematical expression for convolution.

Fig. 1 shows an exemplary room impulse response. Direct-path propagation from the sound source to the microphone gives rise to an initial short period of near-zero amplitude, sometimes referred to as the direct-path propagation delay, followed by a peak. The amplitude of this peak due to direct-path propagation usually it is greater than the reflexions, but a situation exists where the amplitude of the later reflections is higher due to the big distance between the source and the microphone and the reflectivity of the surfaces in the room, in this case late reflections are higher than the

Figure 1: Room Impulse Response

direct path. The early and the late reflections are indicated in the figure as two different regions of the RIR. The early reflection are often taken as the first 50ms of the impulse response [16].

2.2 Wave equation

The sound can be modeled as a superposition of plane waves [11]. In order to make the problem feasible, several simplifications are made: The medium in which the waves moves is homogeneous and its characteristics are independent of the wave amplitude. The wave can be described for one dimension by the following equation:

$$\frac{\partial^2 p}{\partial x^2} = \frac{1}{c^2} \frac{\partial^2 p}{\partial t^2}$$

This notation defines a second order partial differential equation. Where p is the acoustic pressure at position x and c is the speed of sound. The equation describes how the pressure changes based on conditions in its immediate neighbourhood. The equation also says that the rate at which the level is accelerating in time at a given point is proportional to the sum of the rates at which the level is accelerating across each dimension in space at that point.

2.3 Models of room acoustics

Room acoustic modelling technique and especially the room acoustic computer models have developed over the last decades (Rindel, 2002) and highly

accurate models are available today. Three principles are the most common for acoustic computer modelling.

2.3.1 Image source Models

Image source method is based on the principle that a specular reflection can be predicted by mirroring the source in the plane of the reflecting surface. Whilst in a rectangular box-shaped room it is simple to construct all image source for certain order of reflection (Allen & Berkley, 1979) this method is not feasible for an arbitrary room since the number of image sources increase exponentially with the order of reflection, and several hundred reflections are relevant for the audible reverberant decay.

2.3.2 Particle tracing models

Particle tracing models are based on the idea that a set of particles are randomly shot from sources and each particle trajectory is traced as long as it exists. When the particle finds a surface, the particle changes its characteristic depending on surface's characteristics [11].

2.3.3 Ray tracing models

Ray tracing was the first computer model used for a practical design of auditoria (Kroskstad et al., 1968). The source is described by a finite number of rays which travels through space at the speed of sound and are reflected after every collision. The energy is decreased as a consequence of collisions with walls and air absorption. In order to obtain quantitative results it is necessary to introduce receiver surfaces for detection of the sound rays.

2.4 Sound field in a Reverberant Room

When a sound is reproduced inside an enclosed space the listener hears a sum of the direct path and the early and late reflections. The sound energy density due to direct path component is given by

$$E_d = \frac{QW_s}{4\pi cD^2}$$

Where Q describes the directivity of the source (in Omnidirectional Sources $Q = 1$), W is the power output from the sound in watts, D is the distance from the source and c is the speed of sound.

Notice that the energy density of the reverberant sound is independent of the distance D and the energy density of the direct path is related to D by an inverse square law. Similarly the sound energy density due to the reverberant component is given by

$$E_r = \frac{4W_s}{cR}$$

With the room constant, R , given by

$$R = \frac{\bar{\alpha}A}{1 - \bar{\alpha}}$$

Where $\bar{\alpha}$ and A denotes the average absorption coefficient and the total absorption surface area, respectively.

2.4.1 Reverberation time

The reverberation time RT_{60} is the time during which the sound pressure level decreases by 60 dB from its initial level after the sound has abruptly stopped. It can be approximated using Sabine's reverberation equation (Sabine, 1890).

$$RT_{60} = \frac{0.163V}{A}$$

Where V and A is the volume of the room and the total absorption area, respectively.

2.4.2 Energy decay curve

Energy Decay Curve (EDC) is the decay of the squared sound pressure against time when a broadband sound is switched off after having a steady sound energy distribution. The EDC can be obtained from the Schroeder Integral if the AIR of the room, $h(t)$, is known [11].

$$EDC(t) = \int_t^{\infty} h^2(t)\delta t \quad (2.1)$$

In order to compute (2.1), the upper limit of the integration is set to a time instant where the decay curve is close to the noise floor. Then the equation becomes as follows [4]:

$$EDC(t) = N \int_t^{\tau_i} h^2(t)\delta t \quad (2.2)$$

Where N is a constant related to the Power Spectral Density (PSD) of the noise and the T_i is the upper integration limit.

2.4.3 Energy decay relief

The Energy Decay Relief (EDR) is a time-frequency distribution which generalizes the EDC to multiple frequency bands and is a useful way to display reverberation as a function of time and frequency. e.g. $\text{EDR}(0, \omega)$ gives the power gain as a function of frequency and $\text{EDR}(t, \omega_0)$ gives the EDC for some frequency ω_0 .

2.4.4 Early decay time

The Early Decay Time (Early Decay Time) parameter is the reverberation time RT_{60} , measured over the first 10 dB of the decay once the excitation is stopped. In order to compare directly with the reverberation time the result is scaled by a factor of 6.

2.5 Perceived effect of a reverberant room in speech and audio

The clean signal reproduced within a room can be modified by the effects of the room acoustics, known as a reverberation, and it can be seen as a superposition of numerous delayed and attenuated versions of a clean signal. The interaction of these versions produces mainly two effects [16].

2.5.1 Spectral coloration

The spectral coloration effect is mostly due to the stronger early room reflections [13]. The effect over the signal is perceived as a change of color, timber and quality, of the clean signal. The impulse response can be seen as a filter in the frequency domain that explains the changes in the clean signal spectrum.

2.5.2 Temporal tail

The temporal tail effect is due mostly to the late room reflections, typically 50 ms after the direct path signal. The effect over the signal is perceived as a change in quality by increasing the sense of distance. This effect is the contribution of reverberation, and the most perceived by humans. For this reason many studies focus on this part.

In speech, reverberation has a negative effect on the intelligibility, caused by the smearing of the signal. On the other hand, regarding audio signals, the reverberation effect is sought in order to add more brightness, sense of space and harmonic color.

3 DEREVERBERATION

Imagine the following generic situation in which the audio signal $x(t)$ propagates from the source to a microphone through the acoustic channel $h(t)$. The output of the channel is observed using a microphone to give signal $y(t)$. The observed signal $y(t)$ can be described as the convolution between of the source signal and the channel impulse response plus additive noise.

$$y(t) = x(t) * h(t) + b(t)$$

Where $y(t)$, $x(t)$, $b(t)$ and $h(t)$ are the microphone output, the source signal, the background noise and the channel impulse response, respectively. Since room acoustics change slower than the signal it is usually assumed that the Impulse Response (IR) varies slowly over time.

The reverberant signal $y(t)$ can be divided into two components. The early signal component $y_e(t)$, which consist of a direct sound and early reverberation due to early reflections, and the late reverberant signal component $y_r(t)$, which consist of late reverberation due to late reflections.

Also we can formulate the previous scenario by describing the $y(t)$ signal as a superposition of the direct path with a delay and attenuation due to the distance between the source and the microphone and an infinite set of reflections arriving at the microphone at different times and with attenuation that depend on the reflection surface properties,

$$y(t) = \sum_{l=0}^{\infty} h(l)x(t-l)$$

The aim of the signal dereverberation is to find a system with input $y(t)$ and output $\hat{x}(t)$ which is a “good” estimation of $x(t)$. The meaning of *good* depends on the application. Several criteria exist that can be applied in order to find a solution. For example one is by estimating the $\hat{x}(t)$ in the minimum Mean Square Error (MSE). There are three ways to approximate the solution, one is by estimating the RIR and then get the clean signal by using the invert of convolution, the second is by trying to estimate the clean signal by taking into account the reverberated signal and the previous knowledge of it [16], and the last one tries to approximates the solution by taking into account more than one microphones.

3.1 Dereverberation technics for speech

Dereverberation is an active area of research in speech processing for its many applications. Numerous speech dereverberation techniques have been proposed and there are different ways to classify these algorithms, for example single vs. multi-microphone techniques, those primarily affecting coloration vs. those affecting late reverberation, or those that need to estimate the AIR vs. those that do not. In this chapter the main dereverberation techniques are classified by their principle of usage. The techniques are classified in three groups: source-filter model-based speech dereverberation, homomorphic transformation and channel inversion and equalization.

The source-filter model based speech dereverberation is the group of algorithms that have as a main idea to compute an estimate of the clean signal by using techniques as linear prediction, harmonic filtering or statistics, e.g probabilistic model based algorithms.

In the second group of algorithms, the dereverberation technique is based on the idea of signal separation by taking into account cepstral analysis, which is a homomorphic transformation. Two major techniques can be found in this group: Cepstral liftering, and cepstral mean subtraction/high-pass filtering of cepstral frame coefficients.

In the last group, the techniques based on channel inversion and equalization algorithm appear. The approach in this group seeks to estimate an inverse filter of the AIR. The main problem of this kind of algorithms is that the AIR must be known or blindly estimated. As an example of algorithms in this group there are, as a single channel system: direct inverse, minimum mean square error (MMSE) and least-squares algorithm. Also there are a set of algorithm based on a multichannel system, and as an example would be beamforming, matched filtering and multichannel inverse theorem (MINT).

3.2 Source model based speech dereverberation

Different techniques which are based on the speech source model are considered in this section.

3.2.1 Non-negative matrix factorization

The non-negative matrix factorization (NMF) proposed in [12] try to estimate the spectrum of clean speech X_s through a decomposition of the reverberated speech spectrum Y_s into its convolutive components X_s and H_s . In order to emulate human perception, NMF is computed for each of the gammatone sub-bands [10]. The deconvolution process is computed by

using NMF constrained to the non-negativity value of the spectrum and the sparsity of the speech matrix. The mathematical formulation of NMF is

$$Z_s[n, k] \approx Y_s[n, k] = X_s[n, k] * H_s[n, k]$$

Where $Z_s[n, k]$ is the observation sequence, approximately $Y_s[n, k]$, and H_s and X_s is the AIR and Clean signal respectively. The goal is to minimize the error between $Z_s[n, k]$ and $Y_s[n, k]$ by:

$$Min.E = \sum_i (Z_s[i, k] - \sum_m (X_s[m, k]H_s[i - m, k]))^2$$

3.2.2 Iterative deconvolution

The Iterative Deconvolution (ITD) proposed in [9] takes the reverberated signal and it is de-convolved by using, as a initialization step, the NMF decomposition explained before, and then uses a iterative process in order to improve the deconvolution. The ITD is computed for each of the Gammatones sub-bands [14] like the NMF Approach.

3.2.3 Long term multi step linear prediction

Long term multi step linear prediction (LTMSLP) is a technique proposed in [7] to estimate late reverberation by using a linear prediction coefficients. Then the estimated reverberation is suppressed using a spectral subtraction method. The algorithm defines the reverberated signal as the sum of three different parts, the direct path, the early reflections and late reflections.

$$x(n) = h(0)s(n) + \sum_{i=1}^{\tau} h(i)s(n - i) + \sum_{i=\tau+1}^{T-1} h(i)s(n - i) \quad (3.1)$$

where $x(n)$ is the reverberated signal and $s(n)$ the clean signal, $h(n)$ is the IR, T is the duration of $h(n)$, and τ is the number typically around 50 ms that separates the early and late reflections. LTMSLP [18] is used to predict the coefficients $w(n)$ of the late reflections.

$$x(n) = \sum_{p=0}^{N-1} w(p)x(n - p - \tau) + e(n),$$

$$x(n) = \sum_{p=0}^{P-1} w(p)x(n - p) + e(n),$$

where N is the total number of LTMSLP coefficients as well as the number of points of the predicted late reflections impulse response and $e(n)$ is the error. The coefficients are calculated by minimizing the mean-squared error. This algorithm applies a pre-whitening process in the very beginning in order to suppress the short-term correlation and reduce the effect of the production speech system.

In [8] a dereverberation method is presented based on multichannel MSLP for stereo music signals. This approach was tested with real stereo music signals that contain a center vocal signal and instrumental sounds. There is no source code available for this algorithm.

3.2.4 Acoustic echo suppression

The acoustic echo suppression (AES) is proposed in [5] as way to suppress the effect of the far-end signal over the near-end signal. In AES a global delay parameter d and an echo estimation filter (EEF), which is defined usually only from the direct sound and early reflections, are used to model the echo path as follows,

$$y[t] = g_d[t] * x[t - d] + w[t]$$

Then the prediction of the early reflection can be directly computed in frequency domain by

$$|\hat{Y}_{early}[k, m]|^2 = |\hat{G}_d[k, m]|^2 |\hat{X}_d[k, m]|^2$$

Where k and m denote the block time index and the frequency index, respectively. \hat{G}_d is the frequency domain EEF

Since the STFT block length is less than 30 ms, its becomes clear that the late echo is not captured. Hence the late reverberation is estimated as a exponential decay defined by

$$|\hat{Y}_{late}[k, m]|^2 = \alpha_m |\hat{Y}[k - 1, m]|^2$$

whit α_m given by

$$\alpha_m = e^{-2/F_s \tau_m}$$

where τ_m denotes the decay time constant applied for the m th frequency band and F_s represents the block-based sampling frequency of the STFT.

In [5] one method is proposed in order to estimate the τ_m by evaluating the exponentially decaying function in two time instances.

3.2.5 Wiener filter

Wiener filters (N. Wiener, 1940) plays a central role in a wide range of applications, e.g. linear prediction, echo cancellation, signal restoration, channel equalisation and system identification. It can be an infinite-duration impulse response (IIR) filter or a finite-duration impulse response (FIR) filter [19]. The main drawback of FIR filters compared with IIR is that they may need a large number of coefficients to approximate a desired response.

Wiener filter can be applied to equalize the effect of the communication channel distortions. The input/output signals of a linear time invariant channel can be modelled as

$$y(t) = \sum_{k=0}^{P-1} h_k x(t-k) + n(t)$$

Where $x(t)$ is the transmitted signal, $y(t)$ is the received signal, h_k is the IR of the channel and $n(t)$ models the channel noise. Then the Wiener filter $g(t)$ tries to estimate a $x(t)$ as

$$\hat{x}(t) = g(t) * y(t)$$

Wiener filter $g(t)$ can be computed in frequency domain as

$$G(f) = \frac{H^*(f)S(f)}{|H(f)|^2 S(f) + N(f)}$$

where $G(f)$ and $H(f)$ are the STFT of g and h , and the $S(f)$ is the mean power spectra density of the input signal $x(t)$ and $N(f)$ is the mean power spectral density of the noise $n(t)$. The $*$ denotes complex conjugation.

In [21] the Wiener filter is proposed as a filter to suppress reverberation.

3.3 Homomorphic transformation

Homomorphic transformation is well-known in the field of DSP as a method to separate signals combined in a non-linear way by making the problem become linear. Figure 2 shows a homomorphic system for separating signals that have been convolved.

The cepstrum transform was proposed by Oppenheim and Schaffer as a way to dereverberation technique since the simple echoes are observed as a distinct peaks in the cepstrum domain. This approach was not found suitable for complex reverberation models [17] like audio signal models.

Figure 2: Homomorphic separation of convolved signals

3.4 Channel inversion and equalization

Perfect dereverberation can be achieved probably only by the traditional channel inversion. In this section several techniques are reviewed in order to expose their characteristics but will not be useful in this study. In a single channel system it is possible to dereverb a signal (only if the reference is accessible) by minimizing the difference between the reverberated signal and the reference signal using Minimum Mean-Square Error and Least-Squares (MMSE/LS). In a multichannel system scenario it is possible to apply beamforming techniques. This technique is based on the idea of having an array of microphones and extracting the clean signal by combining the signal captured for each microphone [20].

3.5 Commercial plug-ins

There are several solutions for the dereverberation problem in a plug-in format that can be used into a Digital Audio Workstation (DAW). In this section two of these plug-ins are briefly reviewed.

3.5.1 Multi-step linear prediction

This plug-in call it NML RevCon-RR is proposed by NTT Communication Science Laboratories and is based on a Multi-step linear prediction algorithm (MSLP)[7]. The plug-in is in Real Time Audio Suite (RTAS) format and must be run on industry standard DAW Pro-tools. The results obtained by this plug-in on audio signal are more than acceptable, but there is no free, publicly available implementation of this system. In order to adjust de behaviour of the plug-in, there is a set of control parameters that can be manipulated as is shown in fig. below;

Reduction: determines how much reverberation is removed. Parameter values ranges from 0 to 100%, where 0 has no effect and 100 is the maximum amount of reduction.

Figure 3: Snapshot of NML RevCon Plug-in

Release: determines the length of reverberation that is to be targeted for processing. Parameter values ranges from 30 to 500 msec, set in 5msec increments.

Figure 4: Snapshot of NML RevCon Plug-in

Attack Suppression: is an augmentative function designed for dialogue sound that suppresses the reverberation elements that could not be removed using the Reverb Reduction function. This control suppresses the prominent sonic energy following loud passages.

Release Suppression: Suppresses the prominent sonic energy following a drop level.

3.5.2 Izotope

The Izotope RX3 is developed as a set of tools exclusively for audio repair, the plug-in does not need a DAW to run. It is maintained by Izotope, Inc. And there is no free publicly available implementation. Also, there is no

information about the proceedings that the plug-in performs. It's mentioned in this report since the results for this plug-in are remarkable.

4 STUDY

4.1 Research design

In order to do the planned research mentioned above the data must be generated from a source database, where the sound needs to be as clean as possible. Providing the database source from anechoic recordings could be one of the solutions. Therefore, we ensure that the sound recording has no interference due to the wall reflections. The second step should be convolve each sound with different impulse response in order to simulate the effect of the wall reflections and the space. A convolution in time domain is computationally expensive, but in frequency domain it is a multiplication and hence it is less expensive. Each reverberated sound should be dereverberated one by one using the commercial plug-in. Each sound will be processed using a combination of the plug-in parameters in order to evaluate the behaviour of the plug-in. The complete database includes all of the anechoic sounds, reverberation sounds and the dereverberated sounds. The dereverberated sounds have been compared with the respective anechoic sounds to evaluate the effectiveness of the plugin.

4.2 Data collection and sampling

The study analyses the behaviour of the plug-in using instrumental sounds. Therefore, the data needs to be as representative as possible which means different instrumental sounds with different timbres and pitch. In addition, the technique which the instrument is played has a lot of effect on the sound. Hence several playing techniques will be taken into account. The anechoic sounds have been extracted from the database maintained by the University of York and named as Open Air[1], because it is difficult to have time availability inside an anechoic chamber to realize the corresponding recordings and also it is complex to have a musician for each of the instrument that will be studied. The IR used to convolve the anechoic sounds have been extracted from the Aachen impulse response database, and only have been taken into account three IR, with three different reverberation times. All the reverberated sounds have been processed using the plug-in in order to get a clean signal. The plugin has four parameters that can be manipulated, but in this research only two will be taken into account; reduction and release. Each of the reverberating sounds were compared with the respective anechoic sound in order to compute a set of objectives measures. This measures includes Cepstrum Distance, LogLikelihood ratio and FwsegSNR.

In this study one dataset has been created using a set of anechoic recordings with a combination of an impulse response database. The anechoic dataset includes sounds of violin, bass viol, tenor viol, viola, clarinet, trumpet, tuba, bagpipe, drums, speech and operatic voice. In addition the dataset has different types of playing techniques like legato, pizzicato, detache and staccato. Each anechoic recording was normalized, converted to mono and re-sampled at 44.100Hz. After that, each sound is convolved with three different IR extracted from the Aachen impulse response database [15]. The characteristics for each IR are as follows:

Location Name	T20	T30	EDT
Aula Carolina	3.39s	4.49s	0.59s
Lecture Room	0.83s	0.85s	0.26s
Meeting Room	0.25s	0.29s	0.134s

The database with the reverberated sounds plus the anechoic sounds has 152 sounds. Each sound is labelled following the same structure:

nameOfInstrument_technique_nameIR.wav

As an example: a clarinet sound with an ascending arpeggio inside the Aula Carolina will be labelled as follows:

cl_class_c_arp_asc_32_AulaCarolina

The following table shows the meaning of the abbreviations used on the labelled process.

Abbreviation	Meaning
arp	arpeggio
asc	ascending
bvf	bass viol (front mic)
bvb	bass viol (back mic)
chrom	chromatic
cl	clarinet
des	descending
leg	legato
mdv	messa di voce
pizz	pizzicato
sc	scale
st	staccato
t	tongued
tr	trumpet

To develop the study another database was built using the database explained above. Each of the 152 excerpts have been processed by the NML RevCon plugin with 4 different combination of parameters. The parameters are more explained in section 5.1.

Combination	Reduction Control %	Release Control <i>mSec</i>
1	50	30
2	50	300
3	100	30
4	100	300

In this dataset there are 444 excerpts and each one is labelled as follow:

nameOfInstrument_technique_nameIR_reductionControl_releaseControl.wav

As an example: a clarinet sound with an ascending arpeggio inside the Aula Carolina and dereverberated with the parameters 100 control and 30 release will be labelled as follows:

cl_class_c_arp_asc_32_AulaCarolin_rrAS_100_30.wav

4.3 Evaluation

In [6] a set of objectives measures is presented in order to test the quality of the speech enhancement. The best objective measure, extracted from the previous study, is the Perceptual Evaluation of Speech Quality (PESQ) that is given by

$$PESQ = a_0 + a_1 D_{ind} + a_2 A_{ind}$$

Where D_{ind} is the average of disturbance value and A_{ind} is the asymmetrical disturbance value. The parameters a_0, a_1, a_2 can be optimized for the particular system.

Also there is the frequency-weighted segmental SNR (fwSNRseg) measure that is a simpler alternative of PESQ, and it is computed as follows

$$fwSNRseg = \frac{10}{M} \times \sum_{m=0}^{M-1} \frac{\sum_{j=1}^K W(j, m) \log_{10} \frac{|X(j, m)|^2}{(|X(j, m)| - |\hat{X}(j, m)|)^2}}{\sum_{j=1}^K W(j, m)}$$

Where $W(j, m)$ is the weight on the j th bin and K the total number of bins. M is the total number of frames. The $X(j, m)$ is the original signal and $\hat{X}(j, m)$ the weighted enhanced signal.

4.4 Research Tools

To develop the study, the following tools have been used:

PC: Processor Intel Core i3, 1.8GHz and 6GB de RAM

Audio Interface: Edirol UA25

DAW: Avid Protools HD 9 (Trial Version)

Plugin: NML Rev Con v1.0 (Trial Version)

Processing: MatlabR2013

The computation of the objective measures is done by using the evaluation functions from the Dereverberation Challenge Website [2]

4.5 Data analysis and presentation

The software Matlab has been used to analyze all the data generated after the experiments. Several scripts were developed to obtain the results. The results have been designed using graphic bars to make them more understandable.

5 RESULTS

To evaluate the behaviour of the plug-in five analyses have been made. The objective measure used in this analysis is the *FwSegSNR* explained in Section 6.5.

5.1 Speech

Fig. 5 shows a comparison among each female speech sound before and after dereverberation process for each of the three IR cases and with all combinations for the plug-in parameters.

Figure 5: FwSegSNR for each reverberated and dereverberated speech sample

5.2 % Improvements by instrument

In fig. 6, the number of improvements are counted. The improvement is understood to be the increase of the signal to noise ratio, taking as a reference the signal to noise ratio from the reverberated signal. Once the

number of the excerpts that have been improved is known, the percentage is computed by taking into account all the excerpts for each sound. The sounds are grouped by instrument, omitting the playing techniques.

Figure 6: Percentage of improvement for each family instrument after applying the plug-in.

Fig. 7 shows the improvement percentage after applying the dereverberation plug-in for each family of instruments, dividing the dataset into four groups: strings, winds, voice and percussion.

Figure 7: Percentage of improvement for each family of instrument after applying the plug-in.

5.3 % Improvements by Impulse Response

The same analysis made above is filtered by each IR in order to see the effect of the IR characteristics over the dereverberation process.

Figure 8: Percentage of improvement for each instrument with IR from Aula Carolina after applying the plug-in.

Figure 9: Percentage of improvement for each family of instrument with IR from Aula Carolina after applying the plug-in.

Figure 10: Percentage of improvement for each instrument with IR from Lecture Room after applying the plug-in.

Figure 11: Percentage of improvement for each family of instrument with IR from Lecture Room after applying the plug-in.

Figure 12: Percentage of improvement for each instrument with IR from Meeting Room after applying the plug-in.

Figure 13: Percentage of improvement for each family of instrument with IR from Meeting Room after applying the plug-in.

5.4 Clarinet

In this analysis is taking into account the playing techniques, two same clarinet pieces were played with two different techniques, legato and staccato, the results are shown below:

Figure 14: FwsegSNR for the Clarinet sound played Legato.

Figure 15: FwsegSNR for the Clarinet sound played Staccato.

5.5 Viola

Two same viola pieces were played with two different techniques, detache and pizzicato, the results are as follows:

Figure 16: FwsegSNR for the Viola sound played detache.

Figure 17: FwsegSNR for the Viola sound played pizzicato.

6 DISCUSSION

In this section the results are analyzed and commented upon. As it was predicted from the beginning, the plug-in has better effectiveness when it is used in speech sounds and the reason could be because the main goal of this commercial widget is to clean speech sounds. Therefore, the technology behind it works well for sound with speech characteristics.

In this study, the focus has been on the plugin's behaviour with musical instruments and from the results it is possible to extract that the percussion family has better improvement in terms of Signal to Noise ratio, followed by the family of strings and wind instrument. If this comparison is done for each instrument, the Viola's sound improves more than the other instruments after the plug-in processing. Followed by the Bass Viol, bagpipe, flute, clarinet, trumpet and tuba. The comparison among the percentage of improvements for each IR highlight that the IR with a high reverberation time is processed more accurately by the plug-in. However, this appears to be incorrect since more high time reverberation involves more noise, but the explanation might be that the sense of the distance between the source and the microphone seems less in this IR (AulaCarolina) while the two remaining IR seem to have more distance and, therefore, less intimacy.

According to the results, the behaviour of each sound when the IR is changing is independent, meaning that the results for each instrument are not directly proportional to the reverberation time. For example, the flute improves when the reverberation time decreases. However, this improvement is not seen with the sounds of drums, which have better results with a long reverberation time. The dereverberation plug-in enhancements have no correlation depending on the IR, whereas that it depends on the instrument used.

To focus more on the behaviour of the plug-in, two instruments are analyzed in depth. One is the clarinet and the other is the viola. Regarding the clarinet sound, if the same sound played with two different playing techniques (Staccato and Legato) are compared, the results show that the staccato style has more improvements than the legato technique once the plug-in has been applied. Staccato means short attack and release and so this characteristic might be better to differentiate between the instrument sound and the reverberation effect.

Regarding the viola sound, doing the comparison between two other playing techniques (Pizzicato and Detache), the results show that the pizzicato style has more improvements, reaffirming the thesis explained above.

7 CONCLUSIONS

In this section the conclusions are presented, please refer to section 5 (results analysis) if clarifications are needed.

This thesis observes the behaviour of the dereverberation algorithms with instrumental sounds and the aim is to find the strengths and weaknesses when a instrumental recording is dereverberated.

One of the algorithms with most chance of success was the algorithm based on multi step linear prediction due to the existence of one commercial plug-in based on this technique. Since there was no free public code, it was decided to implement the algorithm using the scientific papers provided. This task was extremely complex and there were not enough information available. Therefore, decision to stop the implementation process and do the evaluation with the commercial plug-in was made.

There were used a dataset with 152 excerpts from ten different instrumental sounds, with different amount of reverberation, and a different playing techniques. After applying the plug-in with four parameter combinations for each of the 152 excerpts, the output was compared with the clean versions of the excerpt, without reverberation, in order to extract the objective measure named as fwSegSNR, which gives the evaluation results for each of the sounds.

One way to evaluate the improvements was by counting the samples that had better SNR after the plug-in was applied, in comparison to the ones without reverberation.

First of all, it has been found that the dereverberation of speech works better, because speech characteristics have a more defined range of frequency whilst the instrumental sounds are more varied and thus more complex to manage. Another reason might be because there are more previous studies focused on speech sound, due to the interest in this field for improving the ASR.

It was shown that the best improvement accomplished by the plug-in was with the drums. The drums used on the dataset had the onsets well marked, a fact that helps the plug-in to define the reverberation part. Consequently, if the reverberation is well defined, the reverberation suppression achieves better results.

The string instruments have improved more than those of the wind family, but the results are well behind those findings obtained from speech sounds. The technique behind the plug-in was a particular case of linear prediction. This technique is well-known to work pretty well with speech, but it does not have the same results for other types of sounds. As a re-

sult, another technique must be taken into account in order to improve the outcomes.

8 FURTHER WORK

This section propose different task to accomplish in order to extend this study.

- The database used during this study has only 592 samples, because the time for doing this thesis was finite and each sample had to be processed individually through the plug-in. In order to make this study more representative it would be interesting to enlarge this database, taking into account more instruments as well as more playing techniques.
- Only one dereverberation algorithm has been used in this study. Other algorithms have been tested, but without any significant result on music signals. Therefore, the study was focused on the multi step linear prediction technique. In the future, it would be interesting to extend the analysis to other dereverberation techniques in order to compare the results obtained.
- Although the analysis was made only for the frequency-weighted segmental signal to noise ratio value, it would be interesting to extend this objective measure to other, more subjective ones, based on the opinion of people, since the feeling of space is something subtle and difficult to evaluate objectively.

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9 Annexes

Table 1 – continued from previous page

File	Ref.	CD Mean	CD Med	LLR Mean	LLR Med	FwSegSNR Mean	FwSegSNR Med
adult_female_speech.wav	adult_female_speech.wav	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	35.000	35.000
adult_female_speech_AulaCarolina.wav	adult_female_speech_AulaCarolina.wav	2.779	2.457	0.815	0.086	5.589	7.330
adult_female_speech_AulaCarolinarrAS_100_30.wav	adult_female_speech_AulaCarolinarrAS_100_30.wav	2.456	2.222	0.559	0.442	7.677	9.082
adult_female_speech_AulaCarolinarrAS_100_300.wav	adult_female_speech_AulaCarolinarrAS_100_300.wav	2.456	2.222	0.559	0.442	7.677	9.082
adult_female_speech_AulaCarolinarrAS_50_30.wav	adult_female_speech_AulaCarolinarrAS_50_30.wav	2.633	2.313	0.682	0.553	6.830	8.049
adult_female_speech_AulaCarolinarrAS_50_300.wav	adult_female_speech_AulaCarolinarrAS_50_300.wav	2.633	2.313	0.682	0.553	6.830	8.049
adult_female_speech_Lecture.wav	adult_female_speech_Lecture.wav	3.209	2.801	0.645	0.510	4.680	6.146
adult_female_speech_LecturerAS_100_30.wav	adult_female_speech_LecturerAS_100_30.wav	3.169	2.727	0.606	0.472	5.401	6.792
adult_female_speech_LecturerAS_100_300.wav	adult_female_speech_LecturerAS_100_300.wav	2.962	2.563	0.590	0.473	6.787	7.800
adult_female_speech_LecturerAS_50_30.wav	adult_female_speech_LecturerAS_50_30.wav	3.225	2.807	0.644	0.505	4.967	6.477
adult_female_speech_LecturerAS_50_300.wav	adult_female_speech_LecturerAS_50_300.wav	3.254	2.814	0.620	0.491	5.283	6.754
adult_female_speech_Meeting.wav	adult_female_speech_Meeting.wav	2.330	1.904	0.356	0.271	8.171	9.618
adult_female_speech_MeetingrrAS_100_30.wav	adult_female_speech_MeetingrrAS_100_30.wav	2.280	1.878	0.342	0.255	8.875	10.053
adult_female_speech_MeetingrrAS_100_300.wav	adult_female_speech_MeetingrrAS_100_300.wav	2.319	1.966	0.432	0.279	9.716	10.670
adult_female_speech_MeetingrrAS_50_30.wav	adult_female_speech_MeetingrrAS_50_30.wav	2.372	1.936	0.381	0.276	8.297	9.486
adult_female_speech_MeetingrrAS_50_300.wav	adult_female_speech_MeetingrrAS_50_300.wav	2.467	2.051	0.394	0.263	8.422	9.467
bagpipe_music.wav	bagpipe_music.wav	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	35.000	35.000
bagpipe_music_AulaCarolina.wav	bagpipe_music_AulaCarolina.wav	0.752	0.645	0.400	0.397	11.146	11.002
bagpipe_music_AulaCarolinarrAS_100_30.wav	bagpipe_music_AulaCarolinarrAS_100_30.wav	0.872	0.768	0.322	0.312	9.506	9.545
bagpipe_music_AulaCarolinarrAS_100_300.wav	bagpipe_music_AulaCarolinarrAS_100_300.wav	1.028	0.972	0.497	0.513	8.029	8.147
bagpipe_music_AulaCarolinarrAS_50_30.wav	bagpipe_music_AulaCarolinarrAS_50_30.wav	0.836	0.734	0.324	0.315	10.667	10.698
bagpipe_music_AulaCarolinarrAS_50_300.wav	bagpipe_music_AulaCarolinarrAS_50_300.wav	0.919	0.821	0.306	0.297	11.270	11.270
bagpipe_music_Lecture.wav	bagpipe_music_Lecture.wav	0.971	0.834	0.298	0.280	10.964	10.814
bagpipe_music_LecturerAS_100_30.wav	bagpipe_music_LecturerAS_100_30.wav	1.069	0.918	0.601	0.589	7.466	7.314
bagpipe_music_LecturerAS_100_300.wav	bagpipe_music_LecturerAS_100_300.wav	1.163	1.017	0.777	0.808	6.903	7.003
bagpipe_music_LecturerAS_50_30.wav	bagpipe_music_LecturerAS_50_30.wav	1.028	0.905	0.265	0.263	10.877	10.760
bagpipe_music_LecturerAS_50_300.wav	bagpipe_music_LecturerAS_50_300.wav	1.108	0.982	0.314	0.302	12.294	12.159
bagpipe_music_Meeting.wav	bagpipe_music_Meeting.wav	0.782	0.709	0.364	0.383	11.158	10.883
bagpipe_music_MeetingrrAS_100_30.wav	bagpipe_music_MeetingrrAS_100_30.wav	0.918	0.809	0.696	0.692	8.307	8.572
bagpipe_music_MeetingrrAS_100_300.wav	bagpipe_music_MeetingrrAS_100_300.wav	1.083	0.998	1.022	1.049	5.996	5.922
bagpipe_music_MeetingrrAS_50_30.wav	bagpipe_music_MeetingrrAS_50_30.wav	0.847	0.766	0.346	0.324	13.129	13.102
bagpipe_music_MeetingrrAS_50_300.wav	bagpipe_music_MeetingrrAS_50_300.wav	0.928	0.840	0.399	0.365	13.443	13.480
bagpipe_steady_chord.wav	bagpipe_steady_chord.wav	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	35.000	35.000
bagpipe_steady_chord_AulaCarolina.wav	bagpipe_steady_chord_AulaCarolina.wav	0.691	0.631	0.348	0.343	11.012	10.813
bagpipe_steady_chord_AulaCarolinarrAS_100_30.wav	bagpipe_steady_chord_AulaCarolinarrAS_100_30.wav	0.877	0.779	0.518	0.486	5.384	5.458
bagpipe_steady_chord_AulaCarolinarrAS_100_300.wav	bagpipe_steady_chord_AulaCarolinarrAS_100_300.wav	0.958	0.874	0.437	0.429	7.652	7.934
bagpipe_steady_chord_AulaCarolinarrAS_50_30.wav	bagpipe_steady_chord_AulaCarolinarrAS_50_30.wav	0.727	0.665	0.264	0.262	10.022	9.972
bagpipe_steady_chord_AulaCarolinarrAS_50_300.wav	bagpipe_steady_chord_AulaCarolinarrAS_50_300.wav	0.811	0.751	0.223	0.220	12.948	13.835
bagpipe_steady_chord_Lecture.wav	bagpipe_steady_chord_Lecture.wav	0.910	0.831	0.177	0.178	12.890	12.754
bagpipe_steady_chord_LecturerAS_100_30.wav	bagpipe_steady_chord_LecturerAS_100_30.wav	0.994	0.902	0.926	0.967	5.091	5.025
bagpipe_steady_chord_LecturerAS_100_300.wav	bagpipe_steady_chord_LecturerAS_100_300.wav	1.100	1.017	0.847	0.881	5.714	5.924
bagpipe_steady_chord_LecturerAS_50_30.wav	bagpipe_steady_chord_LecturerAS_50_30.wav	0.973	0.883	0.157	0.153	12.911	12.683
bagpipe_steady_chord_LecturerAS_50_300.wav	bagpipe_steady_chord_LecturerAS_50_300.wav	1.033	0.929	0.232	0.230	12.230	12.079
bagpipe_steady_chord_Meeting.wav	bagpipe_steady_chord_Meeting.wav	0.721	0.674	0.130	0.126	11.269	11.121
bagpipe_steady_chord_MeetingrrAS_100_30.wav	bagpipe_steady_chord_MeetingrrAS_100_30.wav	0.843	0.762	0.873	0.914	3.859	3.902
bagpipe_steady_chord_MeetingrrAS_100_300.wav	bagpipe_steady_chord_MeetingrrAS_100_300.wav	1.050	0.976	0.883	0.873	5.798	5.775
bagpipe_steady_chord_MeetingrrAS_50_30.wav	bagpipe_steady_chord_MeetingrrAS_50_30.wav	0.792	0.721	0.205	0.208	13.867	13.890
bagpipe_steady_chord_MeetingrrAS_50_300.wav	bagpipe_steady_chord_MeetingrrAS_50_300.wav	0.856	0.777	0.302	0.284	12.244	12.252

Continued on next page

Table 1 – continued from previous page

File	Ref.	CD Mean	CD Med	LLR Mean	LLR Med	FwSegSNR Mean	FwSegSNR Med
bvbsc2.wav		0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	35.000	35.000
bvbsc2_AulaCarolina.wav		2.134	1.831	1.318	1.342	4.203	3.974
bvbsc2_AulaCarolinarrAS_100_300.wav		4.397	4.557	1.318	1.342	0.877	0.346
bvbsc2_AulaCarolinarrAS_100_300.wav		5.131	5.365	1.446	1.619	2.343	0.404
bvbsc2_AulaCarolinarrAS_50_300.wav		4.191	4.183	1.345	1.405	1.405	0.203
bvbsc2_AulaCarolinarrAS_50_300.wav		4.200	4.157	1.410	1.505	1.835	0.216
bvbsc2_Lecture.wav		2.106	1.822	1.796	1.955	5.196	5.075
bvbsc2_LecturerrAS_100_300.wav		1.433	1.385	0.886	0.896	5.187	5.006
bvbsc2_LecturerrAS_100_300.wav		1.412	1.368	0.844	0.838	3.921	3.966
bvbsc2_LecturerrAS_50_300.wav		1.516	1.467	0.177	0.163	12.412	12.332
bvbsc2_LecturerrAS_50_300.wav		1.650	1.595	0.488	0.342	7.399	7.272
bvbsc2_Meeting.wav		2.109	1.850	1.687	1.775	4.734	4.420
bvbsc2_MeetingrAS_100_300.wav		1.273	1.212	1.112	1.124	4.021	3.865
bvbsc2_MeetingrAS_100_300.wav		1.356	1.307	0.888	0.906	4.599	4.491
bvbsc2_MeetingrAS_50_300.wav		1.596	1.489	0.392	0.288	10.214	10.004
bvbsc2_MeetingrAS_50_300.wav		1.586	1.542	0.446	0.290	9.815	9.778
bvbscrep.wav		0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	35.000	35.000
bvbscrep_AulaCarolina.wav		1.119	1.019	0.485	0.471	9.456	9.957
bvbscrep_AulaCarolinarrAS_100_300.wav		1.293	1.195	0.351	0.337	10.342	10.425
bvbscrep_AulaCarolinarrAS_100_300.wav		1.260	1.213	0.340	0.297	7.376	7.456
bvbscrep_AulaCarolinarrAS_50_300.wav		1.327	1.179	0.411	0.410	9.577	9.753
bvbscrep_Lecture.wav		1.348	1.300	0.345	0.340	10.276	10.195
bvbscrep_LecturerrAS_100_300.wav		1.561	1.459	0.275	0.263	9.605	9.718
bvbscrep_LecturerrAS_100_300.wav		1.476	1.327	0.299	0.247	7.697	8.002
bvbscrep_LecturerrAS_50_300.wav		1.832	1.617	0.530	0.442	1.958	2.096
bvbscrep_Meeting.wav		1.632	1.457	0.308	0.247	10.110	10.039
bvbscrep_MeetingrAS_100_300.wav		0.968	0.878	0.268	0.222	10.409	10.701
bvbscrep_MeetingrAS_100_300.wav		1.401	1.305	0.131	0.127	11.700	11.812
bvbscrep_MeetingrAS_100_300.wav		1.458	1.365	0.204	0.163	10.768	10.721
bvbscrep_MeetingrAS_50_300.wav		1.641	1.579	0.493	0.503	5.408	5.395
bvbscrep_MeetingrAS_50_300.wav		1.504	1.443	0.267	0.154	8.703	8.926
bvfpopen.wav		0.000	0.000	0.235	0.151	9.506	9.386
bvfpopen_AulaCarolina.wav		1.224	1.066	0.000	0.000	35.000	35.000
bvfpopen_AulaCarolinarrAS_100_300.wav		1.522	1.346	0.426	0.399	11.176	11.866
bvfpopen_AulaCarolinarrAS_100_300.wav		1.578	1.385	0.323	0.264	11.440	11.440
bvfpopen_AulaCarolinarrAS_50_300.wav		1.764	1.596	0.590	0.565	0.024	0.744
bvfpopen_AulaCarolinarrAS_50_300.wav		1.764	1.654	0.435	0.395	5.095	5.699
bvfpopen_Lecture.wav		1.604	1.536	0.429	0.400	5.378	6.115
bvfpopen_LecturerrAS_100_300.wav		1.822	1.739	0.254	0.221	11.870	12.261
bvfpopen_LecturerrAS_100_300.wav		1.796	1.721	0.690	0.631	5.917	6.390
bvfpopen_LecturerrAS_50_300.wav		1.949	1.911	1.063	1.052	0.911	1.557
bvfpopen_MeetingrAS_100_300.wav		1.853	1.815	0.576	0.514	4.700	5.477
bvfpopen_MeetingrAS_50_300.wav		1.218	1.216	0.635	0.535	5.795	6.322
bvfpopen_MeetingrAS_100_300.wav		1.538	1.532	0.202	0.193	13.051	12.870
bvfpopen_MeetingrAS_100_300.wav		1.555	1.545	0.536	0.506	7.725	7.571
bvfpopen_MeetingrAS_50_300.wav		1.746	1.743	1.021	1.018	1.082	1.082
bvfpopen_MeetingrAS_50_300.wav		1.711	1.731	0.538	0.507	4.270	4.996
bvfpopen_MeetingrAS_50_300.wav		1.711	1.731	0.538	0.457	4.439	4.896

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Table 1 – continued from previous page

File	Ref.	CD Mean	CD Med	LLR Mean	LLR Med	FwSegSNR Mean	FwSegSNR Med
bvfpiece.wav		0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	35.000	35.000
bvfpiece_AulaCarolina.wav		1.250	1.028	0.391	0.385	11,080	11,073
bvfpiece_AulaCarolinarrAS_100_30.wav		1.417	1.274	0.373	0.276	9,545	9,764
bvfpiece_AulaCarolinarrAS_100_300.wav		1.204	1.097	0.424	0.343	10,151	10,151
bvfpiece_AulaCarolinarrAS_50_30.wav		1.434	1.145	0.350	0.347	10,329	10,329
bvfpiece_AulaCarolinarrAS_50_300.wav		1.412	1.171	0.309	0.310	9,884	9,996
bvfpiece_Lecture.wav		1.241	1.118	0.231	0.219	10,266	10,266
bvfpiece_LecturerrAS_100_30.wav		1.572	1.472	0.714	0.648	3,058	3,163
bvfpiece_LecturerrAS_100_300.wav		1.479	1.348	0.870	0.818	4,883	5,035
bvfpiece_LecturerrAS_50_30.wav		1.807	1.653	0.384	0.273	9,494	9,574
bvfpiece_LecturerrAS_50_300.wav		1.563	1.421	0.260	0.224	9,500	9,465
bvfpiece_Meeting.wav		0.982	0.874	0.179	0.169	12,908	12,804
bvfpiece_MeetingrAS_100_30.wav		1.330	1.235	1.137	1.153	1,263	1,460
bvfpiece_MeetingrAS_100_300.wav		1.343	1.253	1.244	1.253	1,854	1,958
bvfpiece_MeetingrAS_50_30.wav		1.318	1.145	0.232	0.190	12,372	12,372
bvfpiece_MeetingrAS_50_300.wav		0.981	0.871	0.178	0.168	12,970	12,861
bvfpizzsc.wav		0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	35,000	35,000
bvfpizzsc_AulaCarolina.wav		0.997	0.866	0.470	0.466	7,054	6,590
bvfpizzsc_AulaCarolinarrAS_100_30.wav		1.658	1.391	0.700	0.672	8,645	8,884
bvfpizzsc_AulaCarolinarrAS_100_300.wav		1.664	1.377	0.773	0.723	5,179	5,261
bvfpizzsc_AulaCarolinarrAS_50_30.wav		1.419	1.258	0.597	0.588	8,136	8,082
bvfpizzsc_AulaCarolinarrAS_50_300.wav		1.654	1.509	0.672	0.642	7,462	7,275
bvfpizzsc_Lecture.wav		1.286	1.078	0.362	0.361	8,939	9,069
bvfpizzsc_LecturerrAS_100_30.wav		1.877	1.571	0.737	0.723	7,293	7,495
bvfpizzsc_LecturerrAS_100_300.wav		1.870	1.574	0.899	0.850	3,060	3,209
bvfpizzsc_LecturerrAS_50_30.wav		1.969	1.756	0.620	0.584	7,582	7,247
bvfpizzsc_LecturerrAS_50_300.wav		1.996	1.763	0.685	0.662	7,496	7,068
bvfpizzsc_Meeting.wav		0.934	0.762	0.173	0.145	11,065	11,521
bvfpizzsc_MeetingrAS_100_30.wav		1.610	1.443	0.485	0.429	8,062	8,062
bvfpizzsc_MeetingrAS_100_300.wav		1.651	1.506	1.196	1.188	2,818	2,841
bvfpizzsc_MeetingrAS_50_30.wav		1.448	1.334	0.381	0.302	11,537	11,598
bvfpizzsc_MeetingrAS_50_300.wav		1.581	1.464	0.568	0.479	10,154	10,199
bvpsc2.wav		0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	35,000	35,000
bvpsc2_AulaCarolina.wav		1.065	0.966	0.416	0.408	12,613	12,717
bvpsc2_AulaCarolinarrAS_100_30.wav		1.325	1.264	0.406	0.381	9,085	8,865
bvpsc2_AulaCarolinarrAS_100_300.wav		1.316	1.268	0.496	0.444	7,114	7,181
bvpsc2_AulaCarolinarrAS_50_30.wav		1.499	1.433	0.330	0.328	10,782	10,903
bvpsc2_AulaCarolinarrAS_50_300.wav		1.576	1.542	0.368	0.342	9,864	9,756
bvpsc2_Lecture.wav		1.294	1.241	0.233	0.215	13,401	13,620
bvpsc2_LecturerrAS_100_30.wav		1.543	1.499	1.116	1.070	1,941	1,890
bvpsc2_LecturerrAS_100_300.wav		1.544	1.505	0.863	0.805	3,436	3,423
bvpsc2_LecturerrAS_50_30.wav		1.628	1.614	0.232	0.213	12,033	11,961
bvpsc2_LecturerrAS_50_300.wav		1.799	1.770	0.599	0.518	7,344	7,200
bvpsc2_Meeting.wav		1.134	1.071	0.159	0.154	11,772	11,686
bvpsc2_MeetingrAS_100_30.wav		1.358	1.332	1.106	1.071	2,868	2,631
bvpsc2_MeetingrAS_100_300.wav		1.398	1.371	0.829	0.789	4,651	4,655
bvpsc2_MeetingrAS_50_30.wav		1.659	1.642	0.302	0.233	10,762	10,665
bvpsc2_MeetingrAS_50_300.wav		1.628	1.593	0.486	0.408	10,066	9,780

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Table 1 – continued from previous page

File	Ref.	CD Mean	CD Med	LLR Mean	LLR Med	FwSegSNR Mean	FwSegSNR Med
bvfscrep.wav		0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	35.000	35.000
bvfscrep_AulaCarolina.wav		1.317	1.171	0.511	0.495	9.332	9.896
bvfscrep_AulaCarolinarrAS_100_30.wav		1.480	1.397	0.360	0.323	10.475	10.524
bvfscrep_AulaCarolinarrAS_100_300.wav		1.394	1.294	0.380	0.326	7.133	7.583
bvfscrep_AulaCarolinarrAS_50_30.wav		1.475	1.323	0.432	0.422	9.555	9.974
bvfscrep_AulaCarolinarrAS_50_300.wav		1.546	1.434	0.363	0.343	10.007	10.328
bvfscrep_Lecture.wav		1.516	1.327	0.326	0.307	9.265	9.360
bvfscrep_LecturrAS_100_30.wav		1.761	1.590	0.433	0.333	6.528	6.878
bvfscrep_LecturrAS_100_300.wav		1.749	1.541	0.741	0.665	1.964	2.247
bvfscrep_LecturrAS_50_30.wav		1.962	1.710	0.356	0.288	9.589	10.019
bvfscrep_LecturrAS_50_300.wav		1.784	1.558	0.316	0.267	9.470	9.844
bvfscrep_Meeting.wav		1.120	1.008	0.147	0.139	11.512	11.546
bvfscrep_MeetingrAS_100_30.wav		1.514	1.403	0.490	0.441	7.824	7.746
bvfscrep_MeetingrAS_100_300.wav		1.598	1.492	0.709	0.681	4.728	4.589
bvfscrep_MeetingrAS_50_30.wav		1.824	1.748	0.356	0.222	8.370	8.324
bvfscrep_MeetingrAS_50_300.wav		1.671	1.597	0.279	0.192	9.525	9.416
bvfscrep_MeetingrAS_50_300.wav		0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	35.000	35.000
bvfscrep_MeetingrAS_50_300.wav		1.597	1.524	0.392	0.358	9.187	9.920
bvfscrep_MeetingrAS_50_300.wav		2.279	1.142	0.252	0.227	10.188	10.569
bvfscrep_MeetingrAS_50_300.wav		2.211	1.965	1.263	1.332	1.128	0.047
bvfscrep_MeetingrAS_50_300.wav		2.318	1.904	1.545	1.709	1.063	1.063
bvfscrep_MeetingrAS_50_300.wav		1.889	1.595	0.403	0.332	8.830	9.447
bvfscrep_MeetingrAS_50_300.wav		2.061	1.729	0.492	0.427	8.383	8.752
bvfscrep_MeetingrAS_50_300.wav		0.910	0.807	0.208	0.148	12.279	12.884
bvfscrep_MeetingrAS_100_30.wav		2.116	1.933	1.456	1.464	3.530	2.689
bvfscrep_MeetingrAS_100_300.wav		2.185	1.857	1.599	1.849	2.859	1.722
bvfscrep_MeetingrAS_50_30.wav		1.527	1.280	0.275	0.178	11.214	11.454
bvfscrep_MeetingrAS_50_300.wav		1.904	1.844	0.400	0.341	9.529	9.593
bvfscrep_MeetingrAS_50_300.wav		0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	35.000	35.000
bvfscrep_MeetingrAS_50_300.wav		0.639	0.593	0.400	0.392	12.993	13.070
bvfscrep_MeetingrAS_50_300.wav		1.303	0.992	1.836	1.896	2.590	2.606
bvfscrep_MeetingrAS_50_300.wav		1.355	1.006	1.492	1.481	1.922	1.385
bvfscrep_MeetingrAS_50_300.wav		1.600	1.160	1.413	1.531	0.306	0.215
bvfscrep_MeetingrAS_50_300.wav		1.567	1.203	1.027	1.078	5.917	5.582
bvfscrep_MeetingrAS_50_300.wav		0.902	0.863	0.228	0.219	14.513	14.465
bvfscrep_MeetingrAS_50_300.wav		1.303	1.110	1.984	2.000	4.230	3.864
bvfscrep_MeetingrAS_50_300.wav		1.341	1.145	1.897	2.000	1.828	1.594
bvfscrep_MeetingrAS_50_300.wav		1.532	1.255	1.489	1.623	0.710	0.024
bvfscrep_MeetingrAS_50_300.wav		1.499	1.280	1.264	1.252	1.037	1.205
bvfscrep_MeetingrAS_50_300.wav		0.751	0.713	0.144	0.138	11.008	11.105
bvfscrep_MeetingrAS_50_300.wav		1.344	1.061	1.989	2.000	2.133	1.989
bvfscrep_MeetingrAS_50_300.wav		1.397	1.113	1.703	1.698	0.257	0.129
bvfscrep_MeetingrAS_50_300.wav		1.639	1.246	1.755	2.000	2.113	1.736
bvfscrep_MeetingrAS_50_300.wav		1.699	1.507	0.764	0.640	6.464	6.069
bvfscrep_MeetingrAS_50_300.wav		0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	35.000	35.000
bvfscrep_MeetingrAS_50_300.wav		1.549	1.410	1.603	1.640	1.198	1.198
bvfscrep_MeetingrAS_50_300.wav		6.235	6.551	1.998	2.000	4.018	0.589
bvfscrep_MeetingrAS_50_300.wav		4.985	5.175	2.000	2.000	3.645	0.017

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File	Ref.	CD Mean	CD Med	LLR Mean	LLR Med	FwSegSNR Mean	FwSegSNR Med
clclassmdvg32_AulaCarolinarrAS_50_30.wav		3.650	3.748	1.989	2.000	1.325	0.061
clclassmdvg32_AulaCarolinarrAS_50_300.wav		3.922	4.064	2.000	2.000	2.664	0.105
clclassmdvg32_Lecture.wav		1.593	1.457	1.730	1.828	0.797	0.349
clclassmdvg32_LecturrAS_100_30.wav		1.513	1.323	1.916	2.000	0.943	0.931
clclassmdvg32_LecturrAS_100_300.wav		1.447	1.149	1.540	1.539	0.381	0.456
clclassmdvg32_LecturrAS_50_30.wav		0.970	0.906	0.240	0.180	13.558	13.370
clclassmdvg32_LecturrAS_50_300.wav		1.134	1.062	0.571	0.564	1.751	1.978
clclassmdvg32_Meeting.wav		1.584	1.455	1.729	1.759	0.554	0.688
clclassmdvg32_MeetingrrAS_100_30.wav		1.580	1.298	1.951	2.000	8.450	8.601
clclassmdvg32_MeetingrrAS_100_300.wav		1.463	1.175	1.478	1.444	0.394	0.542
clclassmdvg32_MeetingrrAS_50_30.wav		0.995	0.916	0.275	0.198	5.644	6.159
clclassmdvg32_MeetingrrAS_50_300.wav		1.147	1.044	0.490	0.410	5.415	5.811
clclasspiece32.wav		0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	35.000	35.000
clclasspiece32_AulaCarolina.wav		1.088	1.000	0.432	0.401	10.817	10.644
clclasspiece32_Lecture.wav		1.125	0.997	0.329	0.274	10.284	10.394
clclasspiece32_LecturrAS_100_30.wav		1.849	1.542	1.610	1.788	3.915	3.653
clclasspiece32_LecturrAS_100_300.wav		1.983	1.603	1.823	2.000	6.030	6.054
clclasspiece32_LecturrAS_50_30.wav		1.809	1.725	0.921	0.620	5.375	4.976
clclasspiece32_LecturrAS_50_300.wav		2.003	1.839	0.949	0.829	8.196	7.501
clclasspiece32_Meeting.wav		0.895	0.807	0.183	0.139	12.759	13.022
clclasspiece32_MeetingrrAS_100_30.wav		1.771	1.437	1.711	1.960	4.167	3.908
clclasspiece32_MeetingrrAS_100_300.wav		1.915	1.556	1.871	2.000	5.524	5.586
clclasspiece32_MeetingrrAS_50_30.wav		1.800	1.842	0.814	0.507	6.166	5.577
clclasspiece32_MeetingrrAS_50_300.wav		1.916	1.666	0.828	0.597	8.477	7.993
clclassclegdes32.wav		0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	35.000	35.000
clclassclegdes32_AulaCarolina.wav		1.162	1.047	0.398	0.379	10.077	9.753
clclassclegdes32_AulaCarolinarrAS_100_30.wav		1.559	1.352	0.849	0.763	1.993	1.869
clclassclegdes32_AulaCarolinarrAS_100_300.wav		1.774	1.530	1.147	1.146	4.349	4.450
clclassclegdes32_AulaCarolinarrAS_50_30.wav		1.592	1.420	0.430	0.367	9.189	8.814
clclassclegdes32_AulaCarolinarrAS_50_300.wav		1.568	1.463	0.493	0.394	8.931	8.722
clclassclegdes32_Lecture.wav		1.167	1.028	0.319	0.287	11.027	11.151
clclassclegdes32_LecturrAS_100_30.wav		1.700	1.615	0.959	0.824	0.308	0.247
clclassclegdes32_LecturrAS_100_300.wav		1.857	1.735	1.550	1.831	7.501	7.847
clclassclegdes32_LecturrAS_50_30.wav		1.644	1.469	0.539	0.354	9.632	9.314
clclassclegdes32_LecturrAS_50_300.wav		1.456	1.290	0.450	0.340	9.782	9.354
clclassclegdes32_Meeting.wav		0.878	0.742	0.238	0.206	11.658	11.705
clclassclegdes32_MeetingrrAS_100_30.wav		1.684	1.606	1.209	0.981	3.713	3.922
clclassclegdes32_MeetingrrAS_100_300.wav		1.708	1.551	1.606	2.000	6.660	6.586
clclassclegdes32_MeetingrrAS_50_30.wav		1.387	1.213	0.466	0.318	9.091	9.377
clclassclegdes32_MeetingrrAS_50_300.wav		1.359	1.223	0.405	0.265	9.618	9.636
clclasscstacasc32.wav		0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	35.000	35.000
clclasscstacasc32_AulaCarolina.wav		2.539	2.424	1.189	1.479	2.472	7.515
clclasscstacasc32_AulaCarolinarrAS_100_30.wav		2.280	2.188	1.116	1.301	0.254	3.095
clclasscstacasc32_AulaCarolinarrAS_100_300.wav		2.280	2.188	1.116	1.301	0.254	3.095
clclasscstacasc32_AulaCarolinarrAS_50_30.wav		2.650	2.614	1.160	1.442	1.792	6.367
clclasscstacasc32_AulaCarolinarrAS_50_300.wav		2.597	2.506	1.135	1.410	1.008	4.594
clclasscstacasc32_Lecture.wav		2.786	2.754	1.091	1.273	1.516	4.893
clclasscstacasc32_LecturrAS_100_30.wav		2.886	2.886	1.064	1.136	0.604	3.954

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File	Ref.	CD Mean	CD Med	LLR Mean	LLR Med	FwSegSNR Mean	FwSegSNR Med
dclasscstasc32.LectureRRAS.100.300.wav	clclasscstasc32.wav	2.765	2.705	1.131	1.191	2.962	6.951
dclasscstasc32.LectureRRAS.50.300.wav	clclasscstasc32.wav	2.950	2.944	1.083	1.243	0.948	4.004
dclasscstasc32.LectureRRAS.50.300.wav	clclasscstasc32.wav	3.006	2.954	1.091	1.240	0.718	3.407
dclasscstasc32.MeetingRRAS.100.300.wav	clclasscstasc32.wav	1.958	1.818	0.502	0.437	4.358	5.016
dclasscstasc32.MeetingRRAS.100.300.wav	clclasscstasc32.wav	2.305	2.007	1.024	0.911	4.595	6.152
dclasscstasc32.MeetingRRAS.100.300.wav	clclasscstasc32.wav	2.305	2.007	1.024	0.911	4.595	6.152
dclasscstasc32.MeetingRRAS.50.300.wav	clclasscstasc32.wav	2.445	2.224	0.680	0.621	3.820	4.308
dclasscstasc32.MeetingRRAS.50.300.wav	clclasscstasc32.wav	2.384	2.057	0.679	0.572	4.711	5.059
dclasscstasc32.MeetingRRAS.50.300.wav	clclasscstasc32.wav	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	35.000	35.000
dclasscstasc32.MeetingRRAS.50.300.wav	clclasscstasc32.wav	2.718	2.654	1.340	1.656	2.140	6.089
dclasscstasc32.MeetingRRAS.50.300.wav	clclasscstasc32.wav	2.694	2.639	1.285	1.552	1.964	5.565
dclasscstasc32.MeetingRRAS.50.300.wav	clclasscstasc32.wav	2.580	2.511	1.241	1.426	1.048	3.746
dclasscstasc32.MeetingRRAS.50.300.wav	clclasscstasc32.wav	2.790	2.726	1.315	1.636	1.719	5.008
dclasscstasc32.MeetingRRAS.50.300.wav	clclasscstasc32.wav	2.727	2.649	1.301	1.584	1.091	3.719
dclasscstasc32.MeetingRRAS.50.300.wav	clclasscstasc32.wav	2.744	2.689	1.208	1.459	1.441	4.738
dclasscstasc32.MeetingRRAS.50.300.wav	clclasscstasc32.wav	2.824	2.750	1.160	1.286	3.305	8.319
dclasscstasc32.MeetingRRAS.50.300.wav	clclasscstasc32.wav	2.878	2.729	1.210	1.323	4.133	8.498
dclasscstasc32.MeetingRRAS.50.300.wav	clclasscstasc32.wav	2.851	2.746	1.200	1.445	1.192	4.564
dclasscstasc32.MeetingRRAS.50.300.wav	clclasscstasc32.wav	2.853	2.707	1.208	1.453	1.077	4.310
dclasscstasc32.MeetingRRAS.50.300.wav	clclasscstasc32.wav	2.019	1.885	0.743	0.706	4.104	4.615
dclasscstasc32.MeetingRRAS.50.300.wav	clclasscstasc32.wav	2.141	1.997	0.908	0.813	5.366	6.788
dclasscstasc32.MeetingRRAS.50.300.wav	clclasscstasc32.wav	2.318	2.049	1.115	1.041	3.522	5.388
dclasscstasc32.MeetingRRAS.50.300.wav	clclasscstasc32.wav	2.256	2.008	0.845	0.798	3.784	4.250
dclasscstasc32.MeetingRRAS.50.300.wav	clclasscstasc32.wav	2.241	1.974	0.850	0.807	4.091	4.323
dclasscstasc32.MeetingRRAS.50.300.wav	clclasscstasc32.wav	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	35.000	35.000
dclasscstasc32.MeetingRRAS.50.300.wav	clclasscstasc32.wav	1.186	0.892	0.473	0.402	9.447	10.540
dclasscstasc32.MeetingRRAS.50.300.wav	clclasscstasc32.wav	1.826	1.238	0.906	0.798	7.220	8.117
dclasscstasc32.MeetingRRAS.50.300.wav	clclasscstasc32.wav	1.781	1.248	1.085	1.037	2.993	3.923
dclasscstasc32.MeetingRRAS.50.300.wav	clclasscstasc32.wav	1.841	1.711	0.552	0.434	9.447	9.924
dclasscstasc32.MeetingRRAS.50.300.wav	clclasscstasc32.wav	1.649	1.402	0.497	0.389	9.631	9.834
dclasscstasc32.MeetingRRAS.50.300.wav	clclasscstasc32.wav	1.453	1.114	0.368	0.260	11.108	13.079
dclasscstasc32.MeetingRRAS.50.300.wav	clclasscstasc32.wav	1.973	1.527	1.042	0.965	4.761	5.793
dclasscstasc32.MeetingRRAS.50.300.wav	clclasscstasc32.wav	1.979	1.552	1.571	1.657	0.585	0.183
dclasscstasc32.MeetingRRAS.50.300.wav	clclasscstasc32.wav	1.964	1.688	0.644	0.457	9.215	10.120
dclasscstasc32.MeetingRRAS.50.300.wav	clclasscstasc32.wav	2.001	1.764	0.755	0.614	8.336	8.686
dclasscstasc32.MeetingRRAS.50.300.wav	clclasscstasc32.wav	1.144	0.877	0.199	0.123	11.409	12.584
dclasscstasc32.MeetingRRAS.50.300.wav	clclasscstasc32.wav	1.843	1.427	1.311	1.250	1.466	1.970
dclasscstasc32.MeetingRRAS.50.300.wav	clclasscstasc32.wav	1.823	1.348	1.680	1.850	1.134	0.496
dclasscstasc32.MeetingRRAS.50.300.wav	clclasscstasc32.wav	1.704	1.470	0.318	0.186	10.920	11.584
dclasscstasc32.MeetingRRAS.50.300.wav	clclasscstasc32.wav	1.571	1.321	0.329	0.172	11.582	12.268
dromarped32.wav	chromarped32.wav	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	35.000	35.000
dromarped32.wav	chromarped32.wav	1.402	1.252	0.373	0.355	10.120	10.120
dromarped32.wav	chromarped32.wav	1.839	1.650	0.660	0.576	7.712	7.859
dromarped32.wav	chromarped32.wav	1.817	1.570	0.974	0.957	3.543	3.567
dromarped32.wav	chromarped32.wav	1.748	1.663	0.483	0.485	9.596	9.899
dromarped32.wav	chromarped32.wav	1.586	1.452	0.403	0.364	9.622	9.763
dromarped32.wav	chromarped32.wav	1.210	1.071	0.258	0.204	11.717	11.725
dromarped32.wav	chromarped32.wav	2.007	1.875	1.024	0.823	3.437	3.686

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File	CD Mean	CD Med	LLR Mean	LLR Med	FwSegSNR Mean	FwSegSNR Med
chromped32_LecturrAS_100_300.wav	1.868	1.671	1.411	1.513	0.191	0.145
chromped32_LecturrAS_50_300.wav	1.877	1.861	0.635	0.501	8.918	8.513
chromped32_LecturrAS_50_300.wav	1.211	1.072	0.256	0.202	11,766	11,726
chromped32_Meeting.wav	0.942	0.821	0.172	0.114	13,581	13,581
chromped32_MeetingrAS_100_300.wav	1.690	1.518	0.966	0.820	4,321	4,193
chromped32_MeetingrAS_100_300.wav	1.672	1.460	1.494	1.646	0.005	0.428
chromped32_MeetingrAS_50_300.wav	1.704	1.698	0.441	0.368	10,667	10,059
chromped32_MeetingrAS_50_300.wav	1.616	1.551	0.366	0.250	11,538	11,433
chromrompartasced32.wav	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	35,000	35,000
chromrompartasced32_AulaCarolina.wav	1.101	0.969	0.376	0.369	10,712	10,712
chromrompartasced32_AulaCarolinarrAS_100_300.wav	1.477	1.276	0.687	0.652	6,508	6,628
chromrompartasced32_AulaCarolinarrAS_100_300.wav	1.581	1.298	1.123	1.157	1,047	0.939
chromrompartasced32_AulaCarolinarrAS_50_300.wav	1.229	1.113	0.336	0.327	10,765	10,444
chromrompartasced32_AulaCarolinarrAS_50_300.wav	1.428	1.327	0.386	0.360	10,337	9,946
chromrompartasced32_Lecture.wav	1.196	1.069	0.244	0.210	10,401	10,240
chromrompartasced32_LecturrAS_100_300.wav	1.583	1.382	0.791	0.802	4,052	4,268
chromrompartasced32_LecturrAS_100_300.wav	1.739	1.485	1.611	1.800	0.885	0.696
chromrompartasced32_LecturrAS_50_300.wav	1.409	1.226	0.336	0.222	10,572	10,488
chromrompartasced32_LecturrAS_50_300.wav	1.478	1.322	0.369	0.256	10,738	10,593
chromrompartasced32_Meeting.wav	0.962	0.847	0.177	0.157	11,062	10,784
chromrompartasced32_MeetingrAS_100_300.wav	1.393	1.261	0.729	0.647	2,888	3,016
chromrompartasced32_MeetingrAS_100_300.wav	1.466	1.239	1.517	1.587	0.721	0.618
chromrompartasced32_MeetingrAS_100_300.wav	1.078	0.948	0.185	0.150	11,593	11,243
chromrompartasced32_MeetingrAS_50_300.wav	1.177	1.046	0.263	0.185	11,062	10,811
chromrompartasced32_MeetingrAS_50_300.wav	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	35,000	35,000
chrommdvced32.wav	0.615	0.581	0.375	0.367	11,725	11,597
chrommdvced32_AulaCarolina.wav	1.560	1.188	1.945	2,000	4,762	4,663
chrommdvced32_AulaCarolinarrAS_100_300.wav	1.579	1.186	1.893	2,000	3,889	4,219
chrommdvced32_AulaCarolinarrAS_100_300.wav	1.786	1.443	1.032	1,162	6,209	5,808
chrommdvced32_AulaCarolinarrAS_50_300.wav	1.673	1.401	0.905	0.964	5,518	5,154
chrommdvced32_Lecture.wav	0.841	0.816	0.230	0.214	14,140	14,487
chrommdvced32_LecturrAS_100_300.wav	1.628	1.350	1.979	2,000	0.095	0.255
chrommdvced32_LecturrAS_100_300.wav	1.675	1.372	1.919	2,000	0.321	0.193
chrommdvced32_LecturrAS_50_300.wav	1.685	1.397	1.379	1,422	0.574	0.077
chrommdvced32_LecturrAS_50_300.wav	1.749	1.483	1.344	1,378	0.262	0.262
chrommdvced32_Meeting.wav	0.681	0.669	0.110	0.098	17,174	16,978
chrommdvced32_MeetingrAS_100_300.wav	1.503	1.187	1.976	2,000	3,018	3,703
chrommdvced32_MeetingrAS_100_300.wav	1.515	1.199	1.968	2,000	0.917	1,120
chrommdvced32_MeetingrAS_50_300.wav	1.719	1.337	1.511	1,741	0.744	1,180
chrommdvced32_MeetingrAS_50_300.wav	1.738	1.365	1.302	1,401	2,885	3,289
chrommdvced32_MeetingrAS_50_300.wav	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	35,000	35,000
chrompiece2bar916ed32.wav	0.988	0.886	0.389	0.377	9,079	9,213
chrompiece2bar916ed32_AulaCarolina.wav	1.216	1.162	1.628	1,867	1,149	1,149
chrompiece2bar916ed32_AulaCarolinarrAS_100_300.wav	1.346	1.165	1.538	1,591	2,150	1,944
chrompiece2bar916ed32_AulaCarolinarrAS_100_300.wav	1.783	1.666	1.051	0.948	5,066	4,382
chrompiece2bar916ed32_AulaCarolinarrAS_50_300.wav	1.543	1.383	0.665	0.581	7,354	7,394
chrompiece2bar916ed32_Lecture.wav	1.074	0.909	0.254	0.236	11,764	12,591
chrompiece2bar916ed32_LecturrAS_100_300.wav	1.600	1.387	1.627	2,000	0.742	1,257

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File	CD Mean	CD Med	LLR Mean	LLR Med	FwSegSNR Mean	FwSegSNR Med
chrompiece2bar916ed32_LecturrAS_100_300.wav	1.603	1.839	1.704	2.000	2.080	2.316
chrompiece2bar916ed32_LecturrAS_50_300.wav	1.878	1.843	0.828	0.605	6.377	6.341
chrompiece2bar916ed32_LecturrAS_50_300.wav	1.476	1.345	0.558	0.451	8.306	9.030
chrompiece2bar916ed32_Meeting.wav	0.874	0.747	0.183	0.116	12.095	12.374
chrompiece2bar916ed32_MeetingrrAS_100_300.wav	1.617	1.442	1.709	2.000	0.238	0.558
chrompiece2bar916ed32_MeetingrrAS_100_300.wav	1.662	1.497	1.745	2.000	0.732	0.883
chrompiece2bar916ed32_MeetingrrAS_50_300.wav	2.162	2.207	0.942	0.562	6.665	7.216
chrompiece2bar916ed32_MeetingrrAS_50_300.wav	1.637	1.508	0.545	0.382	9.826	9.760
complete_tenor_fronted16bit.wav	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	35.000	35.000
complete_tenor_fronted16bit_AulaCarolina.wav	0.851	0.767	0.368	0.367	11.486	11.220
complete_tenor_fronted16bit_AulaCarolinarrAS_100_300.wav	1.186	1.075	0.449	0.424	9.665	9.484
complete_tenor_fronted16bit_AulaCarolinarrAS_100_300.wav	1.256	1.142	0.591	0.519	9.242	9.582
complete_tenor_fronted16bit_AulaCarolinarrAS_50_300.wav	1.347	1.278	0.392	0.315	6.352	7.037
complete_tenor_fronted16bit_AulaCarolinarrAS_50_300.wav	1.274	1.198	0.322	0.269	7.872	7.912
complete_tenor_fronted16bit_Lecture.wav	1.044	0.979	0.222	0.199	12.673	12.647
complete_tenor_fronted16bit_LecturerrAS_100_300.wav	1.236	1.172	0.775	0.780	4.815	4.937
complete_tenor_fronted16bit_LecturerrAS_100_300.wav	1.282	1.212	1.114	1.061	2.926	2.203
complete_tenor_fronted16bit_LecturerrAS_50_300.wav	1.482	1.359	1.166	1.277	0.984	1.769
complete_tenor_fronted16bit_LecturerrAS_50_300.wav	1.344	1.260	0.839	0.827	0.207	0.581
complete_tenor_fronted16bit_Meeting.wav	0.803	0.782	0.183	0.137	13.603	13.801
complete_tenor_fronted16bit_MeetingrrAS_100_300.wav	1.199	1.124	0.967	0.847	5.915	5.721
complete_tenor_fronted16bit_MeetingrrAS_100_300.wav	1.234	1.168	1.211	1.003	2.154	2.370
complete_tenor_fronted16bit_MeetingrrAS_50_300.wav	1.342	1.300	0.592	0.368	4.357	4.640
complete_tenor_fronted16bit_MeetingrrAS_50_300.wav	1.351	1.283	0.530	0.392	3.570	3.917
complete_treble_fronted16bit.wav	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	35.000	35.000
complete_treble_fronted16bit_AulaCarolina.wav	0.805	0.742	0.351	0.346	11.157	11.207
complete_treble_fronted16bit_AulaCarolinarrAS_100_300.wav	1.351	1.189	0.770	0.751	3.645	3.647
complete_treble_fronted16bit_AulaCarolinarrAS_300_300.wav	1.324	1.124	0.699	0.680	4.191	4.308
complete_treble_fronted16bit_AulaCarolinarrAS_50_300.wav	1.425	1.335	0.485	0.367	6.534	6.710
complete_treble_fronted16bit_AulaCarolinarrAS_50_300.wav	1.073	0.947	0.284	0.248	10.906	11.182
complete_treble_fronted16bit_Lecture.wav	1.031	0.968	0.191	0.160	9.673	9.752
complete_treble_fronted16bit_LecturerrAS_100_300.wav	1.383	1.312	1.250	1.237	0.309	1.047
complete_treble_fronted16bit_LecturerrAS_100_300.wav	1.398	1.275	1.150	1.026	2.573	2.727
complete_treble_fronted16bit_LecturerrAS_50_300.wav	1.423	1.291	0.603	0.612	4.817	5.254
complete_treble_fronted16bit_LecturerrAS_50_300.wav	1.281	1.156	0.382	0.312	7.099	7.423
complete_treble_fronted16bit_Meeting.wav	0.812	0.765	0.186	0.154	11.701	11.791
complete_treble_fronted16bit_MeetingrrAS_100_300.wav	1.397	1.243	1.477	1.609	0.626	0.229
complete_treble_fronted16bit_MeetingrrAS_100_300.wav	1.322	1.150	1.252	1.189	1.233	1.618
complete_treble_fronted16bit_MeetingrrAS_50_300.wav	1.430	1.325	1.012	0.925	2.251	2.637
complete_treble_fronted16bit_MeetingrrAS_50_300.wav	1.114	0.993	0.467	0.348	7.834	8.153
drums.wav	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	35.000	35.000
drums_AulaCarolina.wav	4.447	4.008	1.221	1.106	2.682	4.284
drums_AulaCarolinarrAS_100_300.wav	4.182	3.624	1.057	0.852	0.819	0.898
drums_AulaCarolinarrAS_100_300.wav	3.967	3.513	0.953	0.670	0.120	0.379
drums_AulaCarolinarrAS_50_300.wav	4.299	3.687	1.165	1.034	2.279	3.623
drums_AulaCarolinarrAS_50_300.wav	4.108	3.260	1.075	0.860	1.717	1.936
drums_Lecture.wav	4.473	3.717	1.070	0.736	3.325	7.629
drums_LecturerrAS_100_300.wav	4.294	3.401	0.869	0.597	3.665	6.546

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File	Ref.	CD Mean	CD Med	LLR Mean	LLR Med	FwSegSNR Mean	FwSegSNR Med
drums_LecturrAS_100_300.wav		3.949	3.133	0.754	0.486	2.106	3.653
drums_LecturrAS_50_30.wav		4.460	3.688	0.934	0.699	3.240	6.608
drums_LecturrAS_50_300.wav		4.340	3.393	0.813	0.586	2.921	4.828
drums_Meeting.wav		3.056	2.329	0.434	0.316	1.626	2.584
drums_MeetingrAS_100_30.wav		2.734	1.986	0.540	0.303	3.196	3.717
drums_MeetingrAS_100_300.wav		2.602	1.974	0.497	0.331	3.077	3.717
drums_MeetingrAS_50_30.wav		3.093	2.411	0.411	0.302	1.936	2.398
drums_MeetingrAS_50_300.wav		2.936	2.252	0.403	0.290	2.603	3.261
flute_arpeggio.wav		0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	35.000	35.000
flute_arpeggio_AulaCarolina.wav		1.858	1.747	0.700	0.435	4.497	8.533
flute_arpeggio_AulaCarolinarrAS_100_30.wav		2.011	1.919	1.283	1.286	5.293	5.213
flute_arpeggio_AulaCarolinarrAS_100_300.wav		1.959	1.848	1.107	1.100	3.613	2.036
flute_arpeggio_AulaCarolinarrAS_50_30.wav		1.961	1.866	0.848	0.695	5.647	6.822
flute_arpeggio_AulaCarolinarrAS_50_300.wav		1.767	1.610	0.766	0.559	6.410	8.021
flute_arpeggio_Lecture.wav		1.596	1.442	0.432	0.310	5.780	6.494
flute_arpeggio_LecturrAS_100_30.wav		1.978	1.776	1.550	1.681	5.169	4.930
flute_arpeggio_LecturrAS_100_300.wav		1.938	1.709	1.379	1.439	2.045	0.955
flute_arpeggio_LecturrAS_50_30.wav		1.681	1.523	0.800	0.633	8.371	8.633
flute_arpeggio_LecturrAS_50_300.wav		1.596	1.396	0.754	0.503	8.541	8.725
flute_arpeggio_Meeting.wav		1.099	1.003	0.200	0.167	11.454	11.627
flute_arpeggio_MeetingrAS_100_30.wav		1.446	1.431	1.668	2.000	3.328	3.450
flute_arpeggio_MeetingrAS_100_300.wav		1.561	1.445	1.509	1.666	1.369	1.252
flute_arpeggio_MeetingrAS_50_30.wav		1.512	1.469	0.799	0.564	10.776	10.863
flute_arpeggio_MeetingrAS_50_300.wav		1.418	1.303	0.800	0.405	10.796	10.738
flute_music.wav		0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	35.000	35.000
flute_music_AulaCarolina.wav		1.261	1.160	0.349	0.347	10.256	10.518
flute_music_AulaCarolinarrAS_100_30.wav		1.446	1.382	0.714	0.687	2.765	2.765
flute_music_AulaCarolinarrAS_100_300.wav		1.450	1.302	0.757	0.749	1.172	1.251
flute_music_AulaCarolinarrAS_50_30.wav		1.327	1.232	0.341	0.332	10.468	10.405
flute_music_AulaCarolinarrAS_50_300.wav		1.367	1.290	0.377	0.331	10.021	9.884
flute_music_Lecture.wav		1.183	1.126	0.206	0.189	11.302	11.358
flute_music_LecturrAS_100_30.wav		1.398	1.324	1.037	0.998	0.043	0.139
flute_music_LecturrAS_100_300.wav		1.562	1.433	1.195	1.123	4.668	4.452
flute_music_LecturrAS_50_30.wav		1.222	1.117	0.253	0.205	11.707	11.647
flute_music_LecturrAS_50_300.wav		1.297	1.166	0.316	0.220	11.515	11.648
flute_music_Meeting.wav		0.970	0.877	0.186	0.163	12.306	12.111
flute_music_MeetingrAS_100_30.wav		1.188	1.134	1.195	1.158	4.436	4.432
flute_music_MeetingrAS_100_300.wav		1.389	1.317	1.198	1.149	1.699	1.724
flute_music_MeetingrAS_50_30.wav		1.033	0.956	0.217	0.166	12.281	12.148
flute_music_MeetingrAS_50_300.wav		1.156	1.075	0.304	0.191	12.035	11.945
flute_musical1.wav		0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	35.000	35.000
flute_musical1_AulaCarolina.wav		1.244	1.160	0.349	0.345	10.389	10.541
flute_musical1_AulaCarolinarrAS_100_30.wav		1.405	1.360	0.669	0.645	4.044	3.911
flute_musical1_AulaCarolinarrAS_100_300.wav		1.446	1.315	0.733	0.717	1.774	1.586
flute_musical1_AulaCarolinarrAS_50_30.wav		1.315	1.233	0.340	0.333	10.525	10.482
flute_musical1_AulaCarolinarrAS_50_300.wav		1.359	1.286	0.371	0.334	10.113	9.933
flute_musical1_Lecture.wav		1.173	1.129	0.197	0.181	11.399	11.399
flute_musical1_Meeting.wav		0.965	0.872	0.183	0.163	12.375	12.090

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File	Ref.	CD Mean	CD Med	LLR Mean	LLR Med	FwSegSNR Mean	FwSegSNR Med
modernviolacma_jorbowlift.wav	modernviolacma_jorbowlift.wav	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	35.000	35.000
modernviolacma_jorbowlift_AulaCarolina.wav	modernviolacma_jorbowlift.wav	1.185	1.020	0.587	0.596	5.645	5.703
modernviolacma_jorbowlift_AulaCarolinarrAS_100_30.wav	modernviolacma_jorbowlift.wav	1.368	1.209	0.462	0.430	8.429	8.825
modernviolacma_jorbowlift_AulaCarolinarrAS_100_300.wav	modernviolacma_jorbowlift.wav	1.415	1.293	0.420	0.358	9.425	9.498
modernviolacma_jorbowlift_AulaCarolinarrAS_50_30.wav	modernviolacma_jorbowlift.wav	1.406	1.244	0.530	0.529	6.302	6.302
modernviolacma_jorbowlift_AulaCarolinarrAS_50_300.wav	modernviolacma_jorbowlift.wav	1.602	1.500	0.465	0.461	6.635	6.325
modernviolacma_jorbowlift_Lecture.wav	modernviolacma_jorbowlift.wav	1.513	1.348	0.452	0.434	7.12	7.817
modernviolacma_jorbowlift_LecturerrAS_100_30.wav	modernviolacma_jorbowlift.wav	1.592	1.479	0.367	0.320	10.789	11.023
modernviolacma_jorbowlift_LecturerrAS_100_300.wav	modernviolacma_jorbowlift.wav	1.698	1.529	0.684	0.513	7.968	7.829
modernviolacma_jorbowlift_LecturerrAS_50_30.wav	modernviolacma_jorbowlift.wav	2.104	2.070	0.455	0.443	8.000	8.143
modernviolacma_jorbowlift_LecturerrAS_50_300.wav	modernviolacma_jorbowlift.wav	2.075	2.057	0.501	0.463	8.332	8.390
modernviolacma_jorbowlift_Meeting.wav	modernviolacma_jorbowlift.wav	1.071	0.874	0.574	0.472	10.815	10.924
modernviolacma_jorbowlift_MeetingrrAS_100_30.wav	modernviolacma_jorbowlift.wav	1.466	1.316	0.315	0.232	11.588	11.616
modernviolacma_jorbowlift_MeetingrrAS_100_300.wav	modernviolacma_jorbowlift.wav	1.551	1.363	0.856	0.621	10.064	9.639
modernviolacma_jorbowlift_MeetingrrAS_50_30.wav	modernviolacma_jorbowlift.wav	1.337	1.117	0.279	0.200	10.111	10.308
modernviolacma_jorbowlift_MeetingrrAS_50_300.wav	modernviolacma_jorbowlift.wav	1.701	1.534	0.447	0.232	8.720	8.872
modernviolacma_jordetache.wav	modernviolacma_jordetache.wav	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	35.000	35.000
modernviolacma_jordetache_AulaCarolina.wav	modernviolacma_jordetache.wav	2.624	2.302	1.040	1.194	2.885	1.137
modernviolacma_jordetache_AulaCarolinarrAS_100_30.wav	modernviolacma_jordetache.wav	2.584	2.299	0.955	1.075	3.976	2.665
modernviolacma_jordetache_AulaCarolinarrAS_100_300.wav	modernviolacma_jordetache.wav	2.097	1.919	0.722	0.761	6.428	5.563
modernviolacma_jordetache_AulaCarolinarrAS_50_30.wav	modernviolacma_jordetache.wav	2.629	2.298	1.018	1.178	3.048	1.503
modernviolacma_jordetache_AulaCarolinarrAS_50_300.wav	modernviolacma_jordetache.wav	2.421	2.104	0.916	1.034	4.917	4.120
modernviolacma_jordetache_Lecture.wav	modernviolacma_jordetache.wav	3.068	2.774	0.914	1.053	1.770	0.425
modernviolacma_jordetache_LecturerrAS_100_30.wav	modernviolacma_jordetache.wav	3.018	2.713	0.866	0.969	3.151	1.652
modernviolacma_jordetache_LecturerrAS_100_300.wav	modernviolacma_jordetache.wav	2.560	2.237	0.837	0.841	3.566	2.638
modernviolacma_jordetache_LecturerrAS_50_30.wav	modernviolacma_jordetache.wav	3.094	2.773	0.908	1.045	1.808	0.376
modernviolacma_jordetache_LecturerrAS_50_300.wav	modernviolacma_jordetache.wav	3.038	2.725	0.860	0.973	1.086	1.086
modernviolacma_jordetache_Meeting.wav	modernviolacma_jordetache.wav	2.043	1.809	0.381	0.319	8.087	7.932
modernviolacma_jordetache_MeetingrrAS_100_30.wav	modernviolacma_jordetache.wav	2.146	1.908	0.401	0.319	9.004	8.954
modernviolacma_jordetache_MeetingrrAS_100_300.wav	modernviolacma_jordetache.wav	2.104	1.962	0.663	0.572	8.932	9.067
modernviolacma_jordetache_MeetingrrAS_50_30.wav	modernviolacma_jordetache.wav	2.130	1.917	0.380	0.319	8.004	7.753
modernviolacma_jordetache_MeetingrrAS_50_300.wav	modernviolacma_jordetache.wav	2.251	2.124	0.353	0.287	8.402	7.852
modernviolacma_jorpizz.wav	modernviolacma_jorpizz.wav	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	35.000	35.000
modernviolacma_jorpizz_AulaCarolina.wav	modernviolacma_jorpizz.wav	1.192	1.025	0.585	0.592	5.646	5.697
modernviolacma_jorpizz_AulaCarolinarrAS_100_30.wav	modernviolacma_jorpizz.wav	1.373	1.211	0.459	0.429	8.431	8.877
modernviolacma_jorpizz_AulaCarolinarrAS_100_300.wav	modernviolacma_jorpizz.wav	1.419	1.294	0.416	0.354	9.429	9.533
modernviolacma_jorpizz_AulaCarolinarrAS_50_30.wav	modernviolacma_jorpizz.wav	1.413	1.244	0.528	0.526	6.132	6.295
modernviolacma_jorpizz_AulaCarolinarrAS_50_300.wav	modernviolacma_jorpizz.wav	1.609	1.498	0.462	0.459	6.638	6.316
modernviolacma_jorpizz_Lecture.wav	modernviolacma_jorpizz.wav	1.515	1.349	0.434	0.410	7.698	7.774
modernviolacma_jorpizz_LecturerrAS_100_30.wav	modernviolacma_jorpizz.wav	1.595	1.465	0.348	0.300	10.823	11.029
modernviolacma_jorpizz_LecturerrAS_100_300.wav	modernviolacma_jorpizz.wav	1.700	1.523	0.673	0.504	7.802	7.522
modernviolacma_jorpizz_LecturerrAS_50_30.wav	modernviolacma_jorpizz.wav	2.083	2.083	0.438	0.434	7.971	8.123
modernviolacma_jorpizz_LecturerrAS_50_300.wav	modernviolacma_jorpizz.wav	2.077	2.060	0.485	0.451	8.354	8.472
modernviolacma_jorpizz_Meeting.wav	modernviolacma_jorpizz.wav	1.079	0.877	0.210	0.177	10.821	10.940
modernviolacma_jorpizz_MeetingrrAS_100_30.wav	modernviolacma_jorpizz.wav	1.475	1.319	0.318	0.238	11.654	11.654
modernviolacma_jorpizz_MeetingrrAS_100_300.wav	modernviolacma_jorpizz.wav	1.559	1.358	0.856	0.610	10.522	9.659
modernviolacma_jorpizz_MeetingrrAS_50_30.wav	modernviolacma_jorpizz.wav	1.343	1.112	0.281	0.202	10.124	10.249
modernviolacma_jorpizz_MeetingrrAS_50_300.wav	modernviolacma_jorpizz.wav	1.709	1.551	0.449	0.231	8.727	8.897

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Table 1 – continued from previous page

File	Ref.	CD Mean	CD Med	LLR Mean	LLR Med	FwSegSNR Mean	FwSegSNR Med
singing.wav	singing.wav	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	35.000	35.000
singing-AulaCarolina.wav	singing.wav	1.829	1.697	0.631	0.469	6.561	9.139
singing-AulaCarolinarrAS_100_30.wav	singing.wav	1.708	1.623	0.563	0.409	7.863	9.882
singing-AulaCarolinarrAS_100_300.wav	singing.wav	1.817	1.718	0.572	0.457	8.288	9.338
singing-AulaCarolinarrAS_50_30.wav	singing.wav	1.788	1.669	0.597	0.453	6.936	8.937
singing-AulaCarolinarrAS_50_300.wav	singing.wav	1.716	1.581	0.585	0.478	7.551	8.067
singing-Lecture.wav	singing.wav	1.459	1.352	0.361	0.259	9.604	11.130
singing-LecturerrAS_100_30.wav	singing.wav	1.782	1.619	0.545	0.382	9.383	10.197
singing-LecturerrAS_100_300.wav	singing.wav	1.863	1.739	0.772	0.675	6.258	6.432
singing-LecturerrAS_50_30.wav	singing.wav	1.476	1.391	0.383	0.255	10.322	11.659
singing-LecturerrAS_50_300.wav	singing.wav	1.616	1.457	0.459	0.346	10.229	10.591
singing-Meeting.wav	singing.wav	1.121	1.037	0.235	0.205	11.796	11.956
singing-MeetingrrAS_100_30.wav	singing.wav	1.506	1.422	0.575	0.316	11.114	10.846
singing-MeetingrrAS_100_300.wav	singing.wav	1.790	1.686	0.801	0.605	5.709	5.209
singing-MeetingrrAS_50_30.wav	singing.wav	1.204	1.197	0.401	0.220	11.814	11.872
singing-MeetingrrAS_50_300.wav	singing.wav	1.473	1.434	0.561	0.360	11.088	10.421
tr1780dfanfare.wav	tr1780dfanfare.wav	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	35.000	35.000
tr1780dfanfare-AulaCarolina.wav	tr1780dfanfare.wav	3.001	2.420	0.709	0.372	7.352	10.811
tr1780dfanfare-AulaCarolinarrAS_100_30.wav	tr1780dfanfare.wav	2.915	2.246	0.799	0.570	3.074	5.633
tr1780dfanfare-AulaCarolinarrAS_100_300.wav	tr1780dfanfare.wav	3.083	2.597	0.757	0.448	2.735	5.099
tr1780dfanfare-AulaCarolinarrAS_50_300.wav	tr1780dfanfare.wav	3.022	2.462	0.659	0.343	7.499	10.332
tr1780dfanfare-Lecture.wav	tr1780dfanfare.wav	3.101	2.537	0.641	0.323	6.622	9.297
tr1780dfanfare-LecturerrAS_100_30.wav	tr1780dfanfare.wav	2.787	2.107	0.546	0.226	7.701	10.510
tr1780dfanfare-LecturerrAS_100_300.wav	tr1780dfanfare.wav	2.851	2.076	0.891	0.773	0.091	1.586
tr1780dfanfare-LecturerrAS_50_300.wav	tr1780dfanfare.wav	3.003	2.368	0.945	0.786	1.066	2.854
tr1780dfanfare-LecturerrAS_50_30.wav	tr1780dfanfare.wav	2.830	2.223	0.503	0.222	7.918	10.106
tr1780dfanfare-LecturerrAS_50_300.wav	tr1780dfanfare.wav	2.246	2.246	0.540	0.245	10.014	10.014
tr1780dfanfare-Meeting.wav	tr1780dfanfare.wav	2.045	1.590	0.272	0.166	7.745	11.309
tr1780dfanfare-MeetingrrAS_100_30.wav	tr1780dfanfare.wav	2.185	1.638	0.723	0.637	2.368	3.514
tr1780dfanfare-MeetingrrAS_100_300.wav	tr1780dfanfare.wav	2.406	1.936	0.792	0.701	3.301	4.477
tr1780dfanfare-MeetingrrAS_50_300.wav	tr1780dfanfare.wav	2.315	1.858	0.331	0.169	8.536	9.722
tr1780dfanfare-MeetingrrAS_50_300.wav	tr1780dfanfare.wav	2.333	1.843	0.397	0.182	9.717	10.663
tr1780dfanfare-MeetingrrAS_50_300.wav	tr1780dfanfare.wav	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	35.000	35.000
tr1780dfanfare-MeetingrrAS_50_300.wav	tr1780dfanfare.wav	1.227	1.089	0.383	0.358	10.666	10.986
tr1780dfanfare-MeetingrrAS_50_300.wav	tr1780dfanfare.wav	1.958	1.811	1.147	1.279	0.562	1.276
tr1780dfanfare-MeetingrrAS_50_300.wav	tr1780dfanfare.wav	2.167	1.966	0.946	0.993	4.997	4.899
tr1780dfanfare-MeetingrrAS_50_300.wav	tr1780dfanfare.wav	1.456	1.238	0.399	0.354	10.677	11.043
tr1780dfanfare-MeetingrrAS_50_300.wav	tr1780dfanfare.wav	1.574	1.391	0.422	0.358	10.526	10.639
tr1780dfanfare-MeetingrrAS_50_300.wav	tr1780dfanfare.wav	1.280	1.135	0.261	0.231	12.301	12.348
tr1780dfanfare-MeetingrrAS_50_300.wav	tr1780dfanfare.wav	2.126	2.085	1.331	1.521	0.650	0.218
tr1780dfanfare-MeetingrrAS_50_300.wav	tr1780dfanfare.wav	2.155	1.970	1.151	1.168	2.154	2.250
tr1780dfanfare-MeetingrrAS_50_300.wav	tr1780dfanfare.wav	1.572	1.335	0.311	0.244	11.195	11.500
tr1780dfanfare-MeetingrrAS_50_300.wav	tr1780dfanfare.wav	2.022	1.921	0.451	0.345	10.089	10.265
tr1780dfanfare-MeetingrrAS_50_300.wav	tr1780dfanfare.wav	1.090	0.944	0.141	0.132	12.130	12.099
tr1780dfanfare-MeetingrrAS_50_300.wav	tr1780dfanfare.wav	2.123	2.044	1.465	1.820	2.339	2.046
tr1780dfanfare-MeetingrrAS_50_300.wav	tr1780dfanfare.wav	1.502	1.885	1.187	1.214	3.206	3.323
tr1780dfanfare-MeetingrrAS_50_300.wav	tr1780dfanfare.wav	1.504	1.219	0.213	0.144	11.403	11.403
tr1780dfanfare-MeetingrrAS_50_300.wav	tr1780dfanfare.wav	1.974	1.898	0.338	0.215	10.760	10.987

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Table 1 – continued from previous page

File	Ref.	CD Mean	CD Med	LLR Mean	LLR Med	FwSegSNR Mean	FwSegSNR Med
tr1967piece7t32.wav	tr1967piece7t32.wav	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	35.000	35.000
tr1967piece7t32_AulaCarolina.wav	tr1967piece7t32.wav	2.780	2.101	0.745	0.420	5.445	9.081
tr1967piece7t32_AulaCarolinarrAS_100_300.wav	tr1967piece7t32.wav	2.131	2.131	0.754	0.480	3.368	5.298
tr1967piece7t32_AulaCarolinarrAS_100_300.wav	tr1967piece7t32.wav	2.898	2.278	0.773	0.500	3.017	4.933
tr1967piece7t32_AulaCarolinarrAS_50_300.wav	tr1967piece7t32.wav	2.801	2.143	0.718	0.403	5.373	8.511
tr1967piece7t32_AulaCarolinarrAS_50_300.wav	tr1967piece7t32.wav	2.831	2.157	0.704	0.391	5.511	8.500
tr1967piece7t32_Lecture.wav	tr1967piece7t32.wav	2.934	2.177	0.667	0.296	5.408	9.000
tr1967piece7t32_Lecture.wav	tr1967piece7t32.wav	2.909	2.097	0.928	0.702	2.517	5.084
tr1967piece7t32_LecturerrAS_100_300.wav	tr1967piece7t32.wav	3.110	2.335	1.122	1.053	1.980	3.426
tr1967piece7t32_LecturerrAS_100_300.wav	tr1967piece7t32.wav	2.956	2.174	0.665	0.292	5.123	8.475
tr1967piece7t32_LecturerrAS_50_300.wav	tr1967piece7t32.wav	2.971	2.163	0.678	0.315	5.025	8.098
tr1967piece7t32_Meeting.wav	tr1967piece7t32.wav	2.319	1.684	0.477	0.210	7.197	10.324
tr1967piece7t32_MeetingrrAS_100_300.wav	tr1967piece7t32.wav	2.297	1.691	0.905	0.772	3.196	4.711
tr1967piece7t32_MeetingrrAS_100_300.wav	tr1967piece7t32.wav	2.496	1.946	0.998	0.900	3.303	5.005
tr1967piece7t32_MeetingrrAS_50_300.wav	tr1967piece7t32.wav	2.388	1.732	0.480	0.219	6.731	9.254
tr1967piece7t32_MeetingrrAS_50_300.wav	tr1967piece7t32.wav	2.442	1.813	0.516	0.255	6.685	9.088
tr1967piece8s132.wav	tr1967piece8s132.wav	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	35.000	35.000
tr1967piece8s132_AulaCarolina.wav	tr1967piece8s132.wav	1.219	1.114	0.401	0.375	10.210	10.310
tr1967piece8s132_AulaCarolinarrAS_100_300.wav	tr1967piece8s132.wav	1.645	1.544	0.561	0.495	7.017	6.304
tr1967piece8s132_AulaCarolinarrAS_100_300.wav	tr1967piece8s132.wav	1.784	1.622	0.778	0.767	1.251	1.475
tr1967piece8s132_AulaCarolinarrAS_100_300.wav	tr1967piece8s132.wav	1.317	1.196	0.368	0.353	9.299	9.412
tr1967piece8s132_AulaCarolinarrAS_50_300.wav	tr1967piece8s132.wav	1.589	1.452	0.403	0.374	8.469	8.479
tr1967piece8s132_Lecture.wav	tr1967piece8s132.wav	1.436	1.236	0.243	0.198	10.981	11.380
tr1967piece8s132_LecturerrAS_100_300.wav	tr1967piece8s132.wav	1.576	1.382	0.811	0.758	1.201	2.053
tr1967piece8s132_LecturerrAS_100_300.wav	tr1967piece8s132.wav	1.774	1.589	1.243	1.175	1.162	0.962
tr1967piece8s132_LecturerrAS_50_300.wav	tr1967piece8s132.wav	1.494	1.292	0.261	0.210	10.328	10.798
tr1967piece8s132_LecturerrAS_50_300.wav	tr1967piece8s132.wav	1.618	1.411	0.343	0.257	9.320	9.399
tr1967piece8s132_Meeting.wav	tr1967piece8s132.wav	1.123	0.950	0.157	0.144	11.762	11.887
tr1967piece8s132_MeetingrrAS_100_300.wav	tr1967piece8s132.wav	1.648	1.594	0.916	0.967	4.880	4.772
tr1967piece8s132_MeetingrrAS_100_300.wav	tr1967piece8s132.wav	1.707	1.512	1.359	1.463	0.022	0.115
tr1967piece8s132_MeetingrrAS_50_300.wav	tr1967piece8s132.wav	1.232	1.086	0.163	0.147	10.980	11.088
tr1967piece8s132_MeetingrrAS_50_300.wav	tr1967piece8s132.wav	1.431	1.264	0.274	0.187	10.442	10.408
tuba_arpeggio.wav	tuba_arpeggio.wav	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	35.000	35.000
tuba_arpeggio_AulaCarolina.wav	tuba_arpeggio.wav	1.302	1.083	0.449	0.402	8.367	10.070
tuba_arpeggio_AulaCarolinarrAS_100_300.wav	tuba_arpeggio.wav	2.291	1.977	1.141	1.251	4.847	5.176
tuba_arpeggio_AulaCarolinarrAS_100_300.wav	tuba_arpeggio.wav	2.180	1.872	1.101	1.199	5.124	5.616
tuba_arpeggio_AulaCarolinarrAS_50_300.wav	tuba_arpeggio.wav	2.212	1.958	1.082	1.179	5.749	5.644
tuba_arpeggio_AulaCarolinarrAS_50_300.wav	tuba_arpeggio.wav	2.024	1.835	0.940	1.018	6.428	6.355
tuba_arpeggio_Lecture.wav	tuba_arpeggio.wav	1.469	1.279	0.376	0.340	9.260	10.038
tuba_arpeggio_LecturerrAS_100_300.wav	tuba_arpeggio.wav	2.464	2.201	0.935	1.040	6.738	6.430
tuba_arpeggio_LecturerrAS_100_300.wav	tuba_arpeggio.wav	2.292	2.088	1.117	1.109	2.619	2.420
tuba_arpeggio_LecturerrAS_50_300.wav	tuba_arpeggio.wav	2.435	2.282	0.784	0.812	7.150	6.832
tuba_arpeggio_LecturerrAS_50_300.wav	tuba_arpeggio.wav	2.074	1.858	0.642	0.564	8.153	8.325
tuba_arpeggio_Meeting.wav	tuba_arpeggio.wav	1.007	0.892	0.122	0.110	11.086	11.253
tuba_arpeggio_MeetingrrAS_100_300.wav	tuba_arpeggio.wav	2.279	2.228	0.577	0.631	9.209	8.889
tuba_arpeggio_MeetingrrAS_100_300.wav	tuba_arpeggio.wav	2.494	2.337	0.990	0.967	3.877	3.620
tuba_arpeggio_MeetingrrAS_50_300.wav	tuba_arpeggio.wav	2.611	2.479	0.660	0.716	7.998	7.326
tuba_arpeggio_MeetingrrAS_50_300.wav	tuba_arpeggio.wav	2.164	1.975	0.490	0.397	9.044	8.784

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Table 1 – continued from previous page

File	Ref.	CD Mean	CD Med	LLR Mean	LLR Med	FwSegSNR Mean	FwSegSNR Med
tuba_music.wav	tuba_music.wav	0,000	0,000	0,000	0,000	35,000	35,000
tuba_music_AulaCarolina.wav	tuba_music.wav	1,088	0,856	0,423	0,391	10,110	11,080
tuba_music_AulaCarolinarrAS_100_30.wav	tuba_music.wav	2,173	1,803	1,434	1,617	4,317	3,919
tuba_music_AulaCarolinarrAS_100_300.wav	tuba_music.wav	2,218	1,823	1,522	1,736	1,018	0,412
tuba_music_AulaCarolinarrAS_50_30.wav	tuba_music.wav	2,228	1,912	1,281	1,484	5,973	5,761
tuba_music_AulaCarolinarrAS_50_300.wav	tuba_music.wav	2,279	2,025	1,232	1,417	5,168	5,186
tuba_music_Lecture.wav	tuba_music.wav	1,312	1,050	0,373	0,330	10,813	11,625
tuba_music_LecturerrAS_100_30.wav	tuba_music.wav	2,164	1,864	1,201	1,298	5,711	5,767
tuba_music_LecturerrAS_100_300.wav	tuba_music.wav	2,235	1,925	1,592	2,000	2,022	1,921
tuba_music_LecturerrAS_50_30.wav	tuba_music.wav	2,121	1,966	0,856	0,902	7,994	8,365
tuba_music_LecturerrAS_50_300.wav	tuba_music.wav	2,145	1,998	0,957	0,883	6,886	7,249
tuba_music_Meeting.wav	tuba_music.wav	1,073	0,821	0,134	0,124	10,448	10,027
tuba_music_MeetingrrAS_100_30.wav	tuba_music.wav	2,463	2,024	1,065	1,174	7,545	7,078
tuba_music_MeetingrrAS_100_300.wav	tuba_music.wav	2,552	2,076	1,570	1,869	1,135	1,779
tuba_music_MeetingrrAS_50_30.wav	tuba_music.wav	2,279	2,024	0,746	0,745	6,956	6,464
tuba_music_MeetingrrAS_50_300.wav	tuba_music.wav	2,598	2,223	1,132	1,226	4,871	4,314

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